

Fast Algorithms for Packing Proportional Fairness and its Dual

Francisco Criado

*Institute of Mathematics, Technische Universität
Berlin, Germany*

CRIADO@MATH.TU-BERLIN.DE

David Martínez-Rubio

*Zuse Institute Berlin and Technische Universität
Berlin, Germany*

MARTINEZ-RUBIO@ZIB.DE

Sebastian Pokutta

*Zuse Institute Berlin and Technische Universität
Berlin, Germany*

POKUTTA@ZIB.DE

Abstract

The proportional fair resource allocation problem is a major problem studied in flow control of networks, operations research, and economic theory, where it has found numerous applications. This problem, defined as the constrained maximization of $\sum_i \log x_i$, is known as the packing proportional fairness problem when the feasible set is defined by positive linear constraints and $x \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n$. In this work, we present a distributed accelerated first-order method for this problem which improves upon previous approaches. We also design an algorithm for the optimization of its dual problem. Both algorithms are *width-independent*. Finally, we show the latter problem has applications to the volume reduction of bounding simplices in an old linear programming algorithm of (YL82), and we obtain some improvements as a result.

1. Introduction

The assignment of bounded resources to several agents under some notions of fairness is a topic studied in networking, operations research, game theory, and economic theory. The allocation obtained by the maximization of the function $\sum_{i=1}^n \log(x_i)$ over a convex set $C \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n$, known as a *proportional fair allocation*, is an important solution that arises under a natural set of fairness axioms (BFT11; Lan+10). It corresponds to Nash bargaining solutions (Nas50) and it also has applications to multi-resource allocation in compute clusters (BR15; JH18; Joe+12), rate control in networks (Kel97) and game theory (JV10; JV07). Other important allocations are linear objectives (no fairness), the max-min allocations (MW00), or α -fair allocations (Atk70; MW00; McC+14), which generalize all of the others. Proportional fairness corresponds to $\alpha = 1$. A natural restriction, that many of these applications require, are positive linear constraints. This results in the *packing proportional fairness problem*, also known as the *1-fair packing problem*. The main focus of this paper is on solving this problem and its dual via first-order methods. Given $A \in \mathcal{M}_{m \times n}(\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0})$, the 1-fair packing problem is

$$\max_{x \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n} \left\{ f(x) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sum_{i=1}^n \log x_i : Ax \leq \mathbb{1}_m \right\}. \quad (1\text{FP})$$

0. Most of the notations in this work have a link to their definitions. For example, if you click or tap on any instance of e_i , you will jump to the place where it is defined as the i -th vector of the canonical base.

We also study the optimization of its Lagrange dual, that can be formulated, cf. [Lemma 11](#), as

$$\min_{\lambda \in \Delta^m} \left\{ g(\lambda) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} - \sum_{i=1}^n \log(A^T \lambda)_i - n \log n \right\}, \quad (\text{1FP-Dual})$$

where $\Delta^m \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^m : \sum \lambda_i = 1, \lambda \geq 0\}$ is the m -dimensional (probability) simplex. We focus on *width-independent* algorithms that additively ε -approximate the optimum of those problems. For the 1-fair packing problem that means, respectively, that we can find \bar{x} in time that depends at most polylogarithmically on the width ρ of the matrix A , and that it satisfies $f^* - f(\bar{x}) \leq \varepsilon$, where f^* is the optimal value. Note that (1FP) has a unique optimizer, by strong concavity. By the same reason, for every two minimizers λ_1, λ_2 of (1FP-Dual), we have $A^T \lambda_1 = A^T \lambda_2$. The width ρ of A is defined as $\max\{A_{ij}\} / \min_{A_{ij} \neq 0}\{A_{ij}\}$, the maximum ratio of the non-zero entries of A . Note that in general width-dependent algorithms are not polynomial. Smoothness and Lipschitz constants of the objectives do not scale polylogarithmically with ρ and thus, direct application of classical first-order methods leads to non-polynomial algorithms. As in packing and covering LP, an approximate solution for our primal problem does not necessarily yield one for the dual problem, cf. (AK08), so we need to study them separately. The current form of our techniques does not generalize to α -fair problems with $\alpha \neq 1$, but generalizing them to these settings is an interesting future direction of research. We note that previous works treat α in $[0, 1)$, $\{1\}$, or $(1, \infty)$ separately, due to the structure of the problems being different. Most works dealing with α -fair functions assume, without loss of generality, that A is given so that the minimum non-zero entry of A is 1 and the maximum entry is ρ . However, in this work, we assume without loss of generality that

$$\max_{i \in [m]} \{A_{ij}\} = 1, \text{ for all } j \in [n]. \quad (1)$$

We can do so because, for our problem, we can rescale each primal coordinate multiplicatively, rescaling the columns of A accordingly, which only changes the objectives by an additive constant. Thus, the additive guarantees we will obtain are also satisfied in the non-scaled problem.

Our primal algorithm solves the problem in a distributed model of computation with n agents. Each agent $j \in [n]$ controls variable x_j and only has access to global parameters like m, n , or the target accuracy ε , to the j -th column of A , and in each round it receives the slack $(Ax)_i - 1$ of all the constraints i in which j participates. This is a standard distributed model of computation. We refer to (KY14; AK08) for its motivation and applications.

Notations We let e_i be the vector with 1 in coordinate i and 0 elsewhere. We denote by A_i a row of A . For $k \in \mathbb{N}$, we use the notation $[k] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$. Throughout this work, $\log(\cdot)$ represents the natural logarithm. For $v \in \mathbb{R}^n$, the notation $\exp(v)$ means entrywise exponential. We use \odot for the entrywise product. Given a 1-strongly convex map ψ , we denote its Bregman divergence by $D_\psi(x, y) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \nabla\psi(x) - \nabla\psi(y) - \langle \nabla\psi(y), x - y \rangle$. We denote by N the number of non-zero entries of the matrix A . The notation $\tilde{O}(\cdot)$ omits logarithmic factors with respect to $m, n, 1/\varepsilon$ and ρ . But note that the rates of our algorithms do not depend on ρ .

Related Work Despite the importance and widespread applicability of fairness objectives, width-independent (and thus polynomial) algorithms for many α -fair packing problems were not developed until recently. Width-independent algorithms were first designed for 0-fair packing, i.e., for

Table 1: Comparison of algorithms for 1-fair packing and its dual. The work of one iteration is linear in N , the number of non-zero entries in A .

Paper	Problem	Iterations	Width-dependence?
(Bec+14)	Primal	$O(\rho^2 mn/\varepsilon)$	Yes
(MSZ16)	Primal	$\tilde{O}(n^5/\varepsilon^5)$	nearly No (polylog)
(DFO20)	Primal	$\tilde{O}(n^2/\varepsilon^2)$	nearly No (polylog)
This paper (Theorem 6)	Primal	$\tilde{O}(n/\varepsilon)$	No
(Bec+14)	Dual	$O(\rho\sqrt{mn}/\varepsilon)$	Yes
This paper (Theorem 10)	Dual	$\tilde{O}(n^2/\varepsilon)$	No

packing linear programming (LP), that have a longer history (LN93). For this problem there are currently nearly linear-time width-independent iterative algorithms (AO19) and distributed algorithms (AO15; DO17). (MSZ16) studied the width-independent optimization of α -fair packing problems for any $\alpha \in [0, \infty]$ with a stateless algorithm and (DFO20) gave better rates with a non-stateless algorithm. Both works use the same distributed framework as ours. For the particular case of 1-fair packing, the latter work obtains an unaccelerated algorithm that runs in $\tilde{O}(n^2/\varepsilon^2)$ distributed iterations. (Bec+14) study the optimization of the dual problem by using Nesterov’s accelerated method, and then they reconstruct a primal solution. However, both primal and dual solutions depend on the smoothness constant of the dual problem, which in the worst case is proportional to ρ^2 , and therefore it is not a polynomial algorithm. In contrast, our algorithms do not depend on ρ at all. Obtaining a priori lower bounds on each of the coordinates of the optimizer is of theoretical and practical interest, since it provides certain amount of resource that can be assigned to each agent before solving the problem. These were studied in (MSZ16) and were improved by (All+18). In Lemma 12, we show a lower bound of this kind for our problem when it is normalized as in (1).

Contribution and Main Results Our contribution can be summarized as follows; See Table 1 for a comparison with previous works.

Accelerated algorithm for 1-fair packing. We design a distributed accelerated algorithm for 1-fair packing by generalizing and extending an accelerated technique, designed for packing LP, that uses truncated gradients of a regularized objective (AO19). In contrast with this technique, ours yields an algorithm and guarantees that are deterministic. We exploit the structure of our problem to obtain a distributed solution, while for packing LP obtaining a distributed or just parallel algorithm that is accelerated and width-independent is an open question (DO17). We make use of a different regularization and an analysis that yields additive error guarantees as opposed to multiplicative ones.

The dual problem. We consider the dual of the 1-fair packing problem. We reduce the problem to optimizing a proxy function by using the Plotkin-Shmoys-Tardos (PST) framework (PST95; AHK12) with a novel geometric separation oracle. Critical to obtaining fast convergence is showing that the oracle parameters decrease when we obtain better solutions. This fact allows to reduce the dependence on ε , and as a result, our width-independent algorithm enjoys a convergence rate of $\tilde{O}(n^2/\varepsilon)$ iterations for this problem.

Algorithm for the minimum-volume simplex problem. Finally, we use the log-volume interpretation to present a new application of the dual problem to the approximation of the simplex $\Delta^{(k+1)}$ of minimum volume that covers a polytope \mathcal{P} , where $\Delta^{(k+1)}$ is given by a previous bounding simplex $\Delta^{(k)}$ containing \mathcal{P} , and where exactly one facet is allowed to move. This results in some improvements to the old *method of simplices* algorithm by (YL82) for LP.

2. A distributed accelerated algorithm for 1-Fair Packing

In this section, we present the main steps of our algorithm for the primal problem, which is a deterministic accelerated descent method that optimizes an objective coming from the 1-fair packing problem, and that encodes the constraints in the form of a barrier. Our algorithm approximates the objective additively and allows to compute each iteration in a distributed manner. We note that (DFO20) also made use of this intermediate objective for the 1-fair packing problem with different constants, but as opposed to their solution, we allow to compute unfeasible solutions during the course of the algorithm, and we proceed with different techniques that allow to achieve acceleration and thus an algorithm with better convergence rates. We defer some proofs to [Appendix B](#).

We reparametrize Problem (IFP) so that the objective function is linear at the expense of making the constraints more complex. That is, we define the function $\hat{f} : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, x \mapsto f(\exp(x)) = \langle \mathbb{1}_n, x \rangle$. The optimization problem becomes

$$\max_{x \in \mathbb{R}^n} \left\{ \hat{f}(x) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \langle \mathbb{1}_n, x \rangle : A \exp(x) \leq \mathbb{1}_m \right\}. \quad (2)$$

Then, we regularize the negative of the reparametrized objective by adding a fast-growing barrier:

$$f_r(x) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} -\langle \mathbb{1}_n, x \rangle + \frac{\beta}{1+\beta} \sum_{i=1}^m (A \exp(x))_i^{\frac{1+\beta}{\beta}}, \nabla_j f_r(x) = -1 + \sum_{i=1}^m (A \exp(x))_i^{\frac{1}{\beta}} a_{ij} \exp(x_j),$$

where $\beta \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{\varepsilon}{6n \log(2mn^2/\varepsilon)}$. In this way, we can work with an unconstrained minimization problem. The resulting function is not globally smooth but when the absolute value of a coordinate of the gradient is large, it is positive, and in that case we are able to take a small gradient descent step and decrease the function considerably. The intuition is that if the gradient is large, then the function value along the segment of the gradient step, as a function of the step, can decrease fast. But it cannot increase fast since there are no large negative gradient coordinates. We depict f_r in [Figure 1](#). The barrier also allows to maintain almost feasibility, as we show in [Proposition 1](#) below. It is chosen to grow fast enough so that a point satisfying $(A \exp(x))_i > 1 + \varepsilon/n$, for some $i \in [n]$, will have an optimality gap that is greater than the required accuracy. On the other hand, the regularizer is very small in the feasible region that is not too close to the boundary.

Let \hat{x}^* be the maximizer of \hat{f} , let $x^* \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \exp(\hat{x}^*)$ be the solution to Problem (IFP), and let x_r^* be the minimizer of f_r . We have $\hat{x}^* \in [-\log(n), 0]^n$ by [Lemma 12](#). Let $\omega \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \log(mn/(1 - \varepsilon/n))$ and define the box $B \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} [-\omega, 0]^n$. We restrict ourselves to this domain and formulate our final problem, that we will minimize with an accelerated method:

$$\min_{x \in B} f_r(x). \quad (\text{1FP-primalReg})$$

Figure 1: Regularized objective f_r (left) and its gradient (right), for a sample matrix $A \in \mathcal{M}_{3 \times 2}(\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0})$. For visualization purposes we show $\log(f_r(x))$ and $\log(\|\nabla f_r(x)\|)$, represented by color, and we indicate the direction of the gradient with normalized arrows. Also, note that we show the results in the original space (i.e., before reparametrizing, so the constraints appear to be linear) but the gradient was computed as originally defined (i.e., after reparametrizing).

Note $f_r(x) \geq 0$ if $x \in B$. We add the redundant and simple box constraints B in order to later guarantee a bound on the regret of the mirror descent method that runs within the algorithm. We show that it suffices to obtain an ε -minimizer of Problem (1FP-primalReg) in order to obtain an $O(\varepsilon)$ -minimizer for the original Problem (1FP).

Proposition 1 [↓] *Let $\varepsilon \in (0, n/2]$. Let x_r^* be the minimizer of (1FP-primalReg) and let $x_r^\varepsilon \in B$ be an ε -minimizer of this problem. Then the point $\bar{u} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \exp(x_r^\varepsilon)/(1 + \varepsilon/n)$ satisfies $f(x^*) - f(\bar{u}) \leq 5\varepsilon$ and $A\bar{u} \leq \mathbf{1}_m$, where x^* is the maximizer of f .*

The intuition about this proposition is that x_r^ε is also a point with low \hat{f} value. By the aforementioned barrier guarantees, it is almost feasible, i.e., $A \exp(x_r^\varepsilon) \leq 1 + \varepsilon/n$, and dividing the corresponding $\exp(x_r^\varepsilon)$ by $1 + \varepsilon/n$, and thus making it feasible, can only increase the objective f by ε .

In the sequel, we will present the different parts of Algorithm 1 and their analyses. In particular, the notation and definitions used are compatible with the choices in the algorithm and most of the parameter choices naturally occur throughout the arguments. Our optimization algorithm starts at the points $x^{(0)} = y^{(0)} = z^{(0)} = -\log(mn/(1 - \varepsilon/n))\mathbf{1}_n$ and updates each of these variables $x^{(k)}$, $y^{(k)}$ and $z^{(k)}$ once in each iteration. They remain in B , by Lemma 2. The role of the three variables is the following: $z^{(k)}$ will be a mirror point and $y^{(k)}$ will be a gradient descent point, in the sense that in order to compute them we apply mirror descent and gradient descent. Then, the point $x^{(k)}$ will be a convex combination of both, that will balance the regret of $z^{(k)}$ with the primal progress of $y^{(k)}$, effectively coupling these two algorithms.

Lemma 2 [↓] *The iterates of Algorithm 1 remain in the box B .*

It is important to note that we do not use the gradient $\nabla f_r(x)$ for our mirror descent loss. Instead, we use a truncation of the gradient. More precisely, the loss we perform the mirror descent step on is the truncated gradient $\overline{\nabla} f_r(x^{(k)}) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ defined as

$$\overline{\nabla}_i f_r(x^{(k)}) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \min\{1, \nabla_i f_r(x^{(k)})\} \text{ for all } i \in [n]. \quad (3)$$

Note that $\overline{\nabla} f_r(x^{(k)}) \in [-1, 1]^n$ because $\nabla f_r(x) \in [-1, \infty]^n$ for any $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$, as the regularizer has positive gradient; see also definition of $f_r(x)$ and its gradient. The truncation allows mirror descent to control one part of the regret, which will not depend on the global Lipschitz constant. Gradient descent will compensate for both such regret and the part that is not controlled by mirror descent.

Let $\Pi_{\mathcal{X}}(\cdot)$ be the $\|\cdot\|_2$ -projection map of a point onto a convex set \mathcal{X} . The mirror descent update can be written in closed form as any of the two following equivalent ways

$$\begin{aligned} z^{(k)} &\leftarrow \Pi_B(z^{(k-1)} - \omega \eta_k \overline{\nabla} f_r(x^{(k)})), \\ z_i^{(k)} &\leftarrow \Pi_{[-\omega, 0]}(z_i^{(k-1)} - \omega \eta_k \overline{\nabla}_i f_r(x^{(k)})), \text{ for all } i \in [n]. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

That is, projecting back to the box, in case of the $\|\cdot\|_2$, consists of simply clipping each coordinate. We bound the regret coming from this mirror descent step by modifying the classical analysis of mirror descent, cf. [Lemma 13](#).

Lemma 3 (Mirror Descent Guarantee) *Let $u \in B$ and choose L as in [Algorithm 1](#). We have:*

$$\langle \eta_k \overline{\nabla} f_r(x^{(k)}), z^{(k-1)} - u \rangle \leq \eta_k^2 L \langle \overline{\nabla} f_r(x^{(k)}), x^{(k)} - y^{(k)} \rangle + \frac{1}{2\omega} \|z^{(k-1)} - u\|_2^2 - \frac{1}{2\omega} \|z^{(k)} - u\|_2^2.$$

Proof Use [Lemma 13.b](#)) below with loss $\ell^{(k)} = \overline{\nabla} f_r(x^{(k)})$, learning rate $\eta = \eta_k$, and regularizer $\psi(x) = \frac{1}{2\omega} \|x\|_2^2$, that yields Bregman divergence $D_\psi(x, y) = \frac{1}{2\omega} \|x - y\|_2^2$. Use that $z^{(k-1)} - z^{(k)} = \eta_k L(x^{(k)} - y^{(k)})$. \blacksquare

Next, we will analyze the role of the gradient descent step. We show in the following lemma a lower bound on the progress of our descent step. Note that this progress could not be greater than $\langle \nabla f_r(x^{(k)}), x^{(k)} - y^{(k)} \rangle$, by convexity, so this is a strong descent condition. In the proof, we will use [Lemma 14](#), which is a crucial generalization of ([DFO20](#), Lemma 3.1).

Lemma 4 (Descent Lemma) *Given $x^{(k)}$ and $y^{(k)}$ as defined in [Algorithm 1](#), the following holds:*

$$f_r(x^{(k)}) - f_r(y^{(k)}) \geq \frac{1}{2} \langle \nabla f_r(x^{(k)}), x^{(k)} - y^{(k)} \rangle \geq 0.$$

Proof We have $x^{(k)} - y^{(k)} = (z^{(k-1)} - z^{(k)})/\eta_k L$ by definition of the gradient descent step. With this, we first conclude that $\frac{1}{2} \langle \nabla f_r(x^{(k)}), x^{(k)} - y^{(k)} \rangle \geq 0$, as $\nabla_i f_r(x^{(k)})$ and $x_i^{(k)} - y_i^{(k)}$ have the same sign for all $i \in [n]$, cf. (4).

We apply [Lemma 14](#) with $y^{(k)}$ corresponding to $x + \Delta$ and $x^{(k)}$ corresponding to x . To this end, we choose $c_i \geq 0$ satisfying ① below

$$\frac{c_i \beta}{4(1 + \beta)} |\overline{\nabla}_i f_r(x^{(k)})| \stackrel{\text{①}}{=} |x_i^{(k)} - y_i^{(k)}| \stackrel{\text{②}}{=} \frac{1}{\eta_k L} |z_i^{(k-1)} - z_i^{(k)}| \stackrel{\text{③}}{\leq} \frac{\omega}{L} |\overline{\nabla}_i f_r(x^{(k)})|,$$

where ② holds by definition of $y^{(k)}$ and ③ holds by the mirror descent update (4). Thus, it suffices to pick c_i such that $c_i \leq \frac{4\omega(1+\beta)}{\beta L} \leq 1$, where the last inequality holds true by the definition of L . In fact, the value of L was chosen to satisfy the previous inequality. Hence, Lemma 14 can be applied. We obtain:

$$f_r(x^{(k)}) - f_r(y^{(k)}) \geq \sum_{i=1}^n \left(1 - \frac{c_i}{2}\right) \nabla_i f_r(x^{(k)})(x_i^{(k)} - y_i^{(k)}) \geq \frac{1}{2} \langle \nabla f_r(x^{(k)}), x^{(k)} - y^{(k)} \rangle.$$

as desired. \blacksquare

Algorithm 1 Accelerated descent method for 1-Fair Packing

Input: Matrix $A \in \mathcal{M}_{m \times n}(\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0})$ normalized as in (1). Accuracy $\varepsilon \in (0, n/2]$.

- 1: $\beta \leftarrow \frac{\varepsilon}{6n \log(2mn^2/\varepsilon)}$; $\omega \leftarrow \log(\frac{mn}{1-\varepsilon/n})$; $L = \max \left\{ \frac{4\omega(1+\beta)}{\beta}, \frac{16n \log(2mn)}{3\varepsilon} + \frac{1}{3} \right\} = \tilde{O}(n/\varepsilon)$
- 2: $\eta_0 \leftarrow \frac{1}{3L}$; $C_k = 3\eta_k L$; $\tau \leftarrow \tau_k = \eta_k / C_k = \frac{1}{3L}$.
- 3: $T \leftarrow \lceil \log(\frac{4n \log(2mn)}{\varepsilon}) / \log(\frac{1}{1-\tau}) \rceil \leq \lceil 3L \log(\frac{4n \log(2mn)}{\varepsilon}) \rceil = \tilde{O}(n/\varepsilon)$
- 4: $x^{(0)} \leftarrow y^{(0)} \leftarrow z^{(0)} \leftarrow -\omega \mathbf{1}_n$

5: **for** $k = 1$ **to** T **do**

- 6: $\eta_k \leftarrow C_k - C_{k-1} = \frac{1}{1-\tau} \eta_{k-1}$
- 7: $x^{(k)} \leftarrow \tau z^{(k-1)} + (1-\tau)y^{(k-1)}$
- 8: $z^{(k)} \leftarrow \arg \min_{z \in B} \left\{ \frac{1}{2\omega} \|z - z^{(k-1)}\|_2^2 + \langle \eta_k \overline{\nabla f_r}(x^{(k)}), z \rangle \right\}$ \diamond Mirror descent step
- 9: $y^{(k)} \leftarrow x^{(k)} + \frac{1}{\eta_k L} (z^{(k)} - z^{(k-1)})$ \diamond Gradient descent step

10: **end for**

11: **return** $\bar{x} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \exp(y^{(T)}) / (1 + \varepsilon/n)$

Output: $f(\bar{x}) - f(x^*) \leq \varepsilon$ and \bar{x} is feasible, i.e., $A\bar{x} \leq 1$. The total number of iterations is $\tilde{O}(n/\varepsilon)$ to obtain an $O(\varepsilon)$ -approximate solution.

2.1. Coupling Mirror Descent and Gradient Descent

We first prove a lemma that shows we can compensate for the regret coming from mirror descent as well as for the rest of the regret. Note the total weighted instantaneous regret $\langle \eta_k \nabla f(x^{(k)}), z^{(k-1)} - u \rangle$ is bounded by the left hand side of (5) up to a difference of potential functions, by Lemma 3. This is a critical part of the analysis: using the truncated gradient for mirror descent makes its corresponding regret not to depend on the smoothness constant, but there is a remaining regret that, crucially, can be compensated by our strong descent condition.

Lemma 5 [\downarrow] Let $C_k \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} 3\eta_k L$, and let $\nu^{(k)} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \nabla f_r(x^{(k)}) - \overline{\nabla f_r}(x^{(k)}) \in [0, \infty)^n$. For all $u \in B$, we have

$$\langle \eta_k \nu^{(k)}, z^{(k-1)} - u \rangle + \eta_k^2 L \langle \overline{\nabla f_r}(x^{(k)}), x^{(k)} - y^{(k)} \rangle \leq C_k (f_r(x^{(k)}) - f_r(y^{(k)})). \quad (5)$$

With these tools at hand, we can now use a linear coupling argument to establish an accelerated convergence rate. Note that the algorithm takes the simple form of iterating a mirror descent step, gradient descent step and a coupling, after a careful choice of parameters. All of which depend on known quantities.

Theorem 6 Let $\varepsilon \leq n/2$ and let x^* be the solution to (1FP) and let x_r^* be the minimizer of (1FP-primalReg). Algorithm 1 computes a point $y^{(T)} \in B$ such that $f_r(y^{(T)}) - f_r(x_r^*) \leq \varepsilon$ in a number of iterations $T = \tilde{O}(n/\varepsilon)$. Besides, $\bar{x} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \exp(y^{(T)})/(1 + \varepsilon/n)$ is a feasible point of (1FP), i.e., $A\bar{x} \leq \mathbf{1}_m$, such that $f(x^*) - f(\bar{x}) \leq 5\varepsilon = O(\varepsilon)$.

Proof We start by bounding the gap with respect to $x^{(k)}$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \eta_k(f_r(x^{(k)}) - f_r(u)) \\
 & \stackrel{\textcircled{1}}{\leq} \langle \eta_k \nabla f_r(x^{(k)}), x^{(k)} - u \rangle \\
 & = \langle \eta_k \nabla f_r(x^{(k)}), x^{(k)} - z^{(k-1)} \rangle + \langle \eta_k \nu^{(k)}, z^{(k-1)} - u \rangle + \langle \eta_k \overline{\nabla f_r}(x^{(k)}), z^{(k-1)} - u \rangle \\
 & \stackrel{\textcircled{2}}{=} \frac{(1-\tau)\eta_k}{\tau} \langle \nabla f_r(x^{(k)}), y^{(k-1)} - x^{(k)} \rangle + \langle \eta_k \nu^{(k)}, z^{(k-1)} - u \rangle + \langle \eta_k \overline{\nabla f_r}(x^{(k)}), z^{(k-1)} - u \rangle \\
 & \stackrel{\textcircled{3}}{\leq} \frac{(1-\tau)\eta_k}{\tau} (f_r(y^{(k-1)}) - f_r(x^{(k)})) + \langle \eta_k \nu^{(k)}, z^{(k-1)} - u \rangle + \langle \eta_k^2 L \overline{\nabla f_r}(x^{(k)}), x^{(k)} - y^{(k)} \rangle \\
 & \quad + \frac{1}{2\omega} \|z^{(k-1)} - u\|_2^2 - \frac{1}{2\omega} \|z^{(k)} - u\|_2^2 \\
 & \stackrel{\textcircled{4}}{\leq} \frac{(1-\tau)\eta_k}{\tau} (f_r(y^{(k-1)}) - f_r(x^{(k)})) + C_k (f_r(x^{(k)}) - f_r(y^{(k)})) + \frac{1}{2\omega} \|z^{(k-1)} - u\|_2^2 \\
 & \quad - \frac{1}{2\omega} \|z^{(k)} - u\|_2^2 \\
 & \stackrel{\textcircled{5}}{\leq} \eta_k f_r(x^{(k)}) + (C_k - \eta_k) f_r(y^{(k-1)}) - C_k f_r(y^{(k)}) + \frac{1}{2\omega} \|z^{(k-1)} - u\|_2^2 - \frac{1}{2\omega} \|z^{(k)} - u\|_2^2
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

We used convexity in $\textcircled{1}$. The definition of $x^{(k)}$ is used in $\textcircled{2}$. Inequality $\textcircled{3}$ uses convexity and Lemma 3. We applied Lemma 5 in $\textcircled{4}$. In $\textcircled{5}$, we substituted the value of τ , which is picked to be $\tau \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \eta_k/C_k = \frac{1}{3L}$ so we can cancel $f_r(x^{(k)})$ in both sides of (6).

The choice of η_k is made so that $C_k - \eta_k = C_{k-1}$ (or equiv. $(3L-1)\eta_k = 3L\eta_{k-1}$), which allows to telescope the previous expression. Adding up (6) for $k = 1, \dots, T$ with $u = x_r^*$, we have

$$\left(-C_0 - \sum_{k=1}^T \eta_k \right) f_r(x_r^*) \leq C_0 (f_r(y^{(0)}) - f_r(x_r^*)) - C_T f_r(y^{(T)}) + \frac{1}{2\omega} \|z^{(0)} - x_r^*\|_2^2.$$

We dropped $-\frac{1}{2\omega} \|z^{(T)} - x_r^*\|_2^2 \leq 0$. Now, since $\eta_k = C_k - C_{k-1}$ we have $-C_0 - \sum_{k=1}^T \eta_k = -C_T$. So reorganizing terms we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_r(y^{(T)}) & \leq f_r(x_r^*) + \frac{1}{C_T} \left(C_0 (f_r(y^{(0)}) - f_r(x_r^*)) + \frac{1}{2\omega} \|z^{(0)} - x_r^*\|_2^2 \right) \\
 & \stackrel{\textcircled{1}}{\leq} f_r(x_r^*) + \frac{1}{C_T} \left(C_0 (n \log(2mn) + 1) + \frac{n \log(mn)}{2} \right) \\
 & \stackrel{\textcircled{2}}{\leq} f_r(x_r^*) + \varepsilon
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Above, ① uses $f_r(y^{(0)}) \leq n \log(mn/(1 - \varepsilon/n)) + \varepsilon \leq n(\log(2mn) + 1)$ and $-f_r(x_r^*) \leq 0$. For the former, take into account that $-\log(mn)\mathbb{1}_n$ is feasible and so the regularizer at $y^{(0)} = -\log(mn/(1 - \varepsilon/n))\mathbb{1}_n$ is at most ε , cf. (15). Recall $\varepsilon < n/2$. We also bounded the last summand by using that $z^{(0)}, x_r^* \in B$ so $\|z^{(0)} - x_r^*\|_2^2 \leq n\omega^2$.

At this point, the only free parameters left are C_0 (via η_0) and T . We set $\eta_0 = \frac{1}{3L}$ so that $C_0 = 1$. And we have that $C_T = 3L\eta_T = 3L\eta_0(1 - \tau)^{-T} = (1 - \tau)^{-T}$. So if we pick T such that

$$\frac{1}{C_T} = (1 - \tau)^T \leq \frac{\varepsilon}{4n \log(2mn)}, \quad (8)$$

we will obtain ②. We will pick the smallest T that satisfies (8). That is,

$$T = \left\lceil \frac{\log(4n \log(2mn)/\varepsilon)}{\log(1/(1 - \tau))} \right\rceil \leq \left\lceil 3L \log \left(\frac{4n \log(2mn)}{\varepsilon} \right) \right\rceil = \tilde{O}(n/\varepsilon).$$

On the other hand, by definition of T as the minimum natural number satisfying (8), we have,

$$(1 - \tau)^T = \frac{\eta_0}{\eta_T} \geq \frac{\varepsilon}{4n \log(2mn)}(1 - \tau).$$

We can use this inequality to show $\eta_k \leq \frac{1}{4}$, for all $k \in [T]$, which is used in the proof of Lemma 5. It is enough that ① below is satisfied:

$$\eta_k \leq \eta_T \leq \frac{4n \log(2mn)\eta_0}{\varepsilon} \frac{1}{1 - \tau} = \frac{4n \log(2mn)}{3L\varepsilon} \frac{3L}{3L - 1} \stackrel{\textcircled{1}}{\leq} \frac{1}{4}. \quad (9)$$

If $L \geq \frac{16n \log(2mn)}{3\varepsilon} + \frac{1}{3}$ then ① holds, and we chose L to satisfy this inequality.

We note we could increase T by a factor $C > 1$ inside of its log in the numerator, so that the error obtained in ② is ε/C . However, the requirement on L above would increase by a factor of C , so we would end up with an extra factor of C in the value of T . Also, the reduction caused by the smoothing already incurs in an ε additive error, cf. Proposition 1. Part 1 of Proposition 1 could use $x = \log(1 - \frac{\varepsilon}{nC})\mathbb{1}_n + \hat{x}^*$ so that inequality (16) ends up being bounded by $O(\varepsilon/C)$, but that would require to have β be C times smaller for (15) to work. This would also require to make L larger by a factor of C so we would also end up having the C in the total number of iterations to obtain an $O(\varepsilon)$ -optimizer.

In conclusion, we obtain an ε minimizer of f_r in $\tilde{O}(n/\varepsilon)$ iterations and by Proposition 1, we get that \bar{x} is a feasible point that is a 5ε optimizer of Problem (1FP). Finally, we note that each iteration of the algorithm can be implemented in $O(N)$ operations, that are distributed, where the bottleneck is the computation of the gradient. From the definition of the gradient, it is clear that it can be computed in our distributed model of computation and that each agent only needs their local variables for the rest of the steps in the algorithm. ■

3. Optimizing the dual problem

In this section, we reduce the dual problem (1FP-Dual) to the feasibility problem of a packing LP, which we call the *proxy* problem. Then, we show how we can use the PST framework (PST95) to

approximately solving the proxy. Our algorithm relies on a carefully built geometric oracle whose *width parameters* can be guaranteed to decrease with the optimality gap. We perform a sequence of restarts, and after each of them we can guarantee lower oracle width. This allows for reducing the overall complexity.

3.1. The dual 1-fair packing problem as a feasibility packing LP

Let $\mathcal{P} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{x \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n : Ax \leq \mathbb{1}_m\}$ be the feasible region of the primal problem (1FP). In this section, we identify (non-negative) covering constraints of the form $\langle h, x \rangle \leq 1$ with vector $h \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n$. Recall we assume without loss of generality that A satisfies (1), that is, the maximum entry of each column is 1. This implies that $e_i \in \mathcal{P}$ for all $i \in [n]$, and $\mathcal{P} \subseteq [0, 1]^n$. For this reason, we also assume in this section and without loss of generality that A contains the constraints $\{e_i\}_{i=1}^n$, i.e., $x_i \leq 1$, for $i \in [n]$. For convenience, we assume they are the first n rows of A .

Let $\lambda^* \in \Delta^m$ be an optimal solution of Problem (1FP-Dual) and let $h^{\lambda^*} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} A^T \lambda^* \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n$.

By strong duality of the Lagrange dual, we can reconstruct the optimal primal solution as $x^* = (1/(nh_1^{\lambda^*}), \dots, 1/(nh_n^{\lambda^*}))$.

This motivates the definition of the *centroid map*:

$$c(h) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \left(\frac{1}{nh_1}, \dots, \frac{1}{nh_n} \right); \quad c^{-1}(x) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \left(\frac{1}{nx_1}, \dots, \frac{1}{nx_n} \right),$$

where $h, x \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n$ are constraints and points, respectively. Despite the two maps above being the same function we distinguish between c and c^{-1} to unambiguously refer to constraints or points. The name of the centroid map is motivated by the fact that, for any constraint $h \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n$, the point $c(h)$ is the geometric centroid of the simplex $\{x \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n : \langle h, x \rangle = 1\}$. Given a $\lambda \in \Delta^m$, we define its associated constraint $h^\lambda \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} A^T \lambda$. In addition, we define the centroid $p^\lambda \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} c(A^T \lambda) = c(h^\lambda)$. Note that we can efficiently compute h^λ, p^λ from λ , and h^λ from p^λ and viceversa. However, we cannot obtain the coefficients λ efficiently from h^λ or p^λ , as this amounts to solving a linear program.

An important property is that h^{λ^*} is the unique constraint of the form h^λ such that $c(h^\lambda) \in \mathcal{P}$, for some $\lambda \in \Delta^m$. It is the optimizer because if h^{λ^*} has $c(h^{\lambda^*}) \in \mathcal{P}$, then $(p^{\lambda^*}, \lambda^*)$ satisfies the optimality conditions. It is unique because of strong convexity of $-\log(\cdot)$; any other dual optimizer $\bar{\lambda}^*$ will have $A^T \bar{\lambda}^* = A^T \lambda^*$. The following lemma shows an approximate version of this property.

Lemma 7 *Let h^λ for $\lambda \in \Delta^m$, such that $Ap^\lambda \leq (1 + \varepsilon)\mathbb{1}_m$. Let λ^* be the minimizer of Problem (1FP-Dual), of objective function g . Then, $g(\lambda) - g(\lambda^*) \leq n \log(1 + \varepsilon) \leq n\varepsilon$.*

Proof As $Ap^\lambda \leq (1 + \varepsilon)\mathbb{1}_m$ we have $A \frac{p^\lambda}{1 + \varepsilon} \leq \mathbb{1}_m$ and hence $\frac{p^\lambda}{1 + \varepsilon}$ is primal feasible. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} g(\lambda) - g(\lambda^*) &\leq g(\lambda) - f\left(\frac{p^\lambda}{1 + \varepsilon}\right) \\ &= -\sum_{i \in [n]} \log(A^T \lambda)_i - n \log n - \sum_{i \in [n]} \log\left(\frac{1}{n(1 + \varepsilon)(A^T \lambda)_i}\right) \\ &= n \log(1 + \varepsilon) \leq n\varepsilon. \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

■

This lemma motivates the minimization of $\max_{i \in [m]} \langle A_i, c(A^T \lambda) \rangle$ for $\lambda \in \Delta^m$ as a proxy for solving Problem (1FP-Dual). Furthermore, if we optimize over the set $\{p^\lambda = c(A^T \lambda) : \lambda \in \Delta^m\}$, we end up with a feasibility problem in a packing LP. However, this set is not convex in general, which is a requirement of the PST framework we intend to use. Fortunately, we can optimize over a larger and convex set while preserving the minimizer. Indeed, define the sets of constraints $\mathcal{D} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{A^T \lambda : \lambda \in \Delta^m\} = \text{conv}(\{A_1, \dots, A_m\})$ and $\mathcal{D}^+ \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{A^T \lambda - \mu \geq \mathbb{0} : \lambda \in \Delta^m, \mu \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n\} = \{h \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n : h \leq h^\lambda, \text{ for } h^\lambda \in \mathcal{D}\}$. For a constraint $h \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n$, we have by polyhedral duality that $h \in \mathcal{D}^+$ if and only if $\langle h, x \rangle \leq 1$ for all $x \in \mathcal{P}$. In other words, \mathcal{D}^+ is exactly the set of positive constraints $\langle h, x \rangle \leq 1$ with $h \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n$ that are feasible for \mathcal{P} . We can think about the optimization of Problem (1FP-Dual) as

$$\min_{h^\lambda \in \mathcal{D}} \left\{ -\sum_{i=1}^n \log(h_i^\lambda) - n \log(n) \right\} \stackrel{\textcircled{1}}{=} \min_{h \in \mathcal{D}^+} \left\{ -\sum_{i=1}^n \log(h_i) - n \log(n) \right\},$$

where $\textcircled{1}$ comes from the following observation: since $h \in \mathcal{D}^+$ if and only if there is $h^\lambda \in \mathcal{D}$ with $h \leq h^\lambda$, and the expression $-\sum_{i=1}^n \log(h_i) - n \log(n)$ is strictly decreasing in every h_i then no $h \in \mathcal{D}^+ \setminus \mathcal{D}$ could ever minimize the right hand side. Consequently, the minimizer of both problems is the same. This results in the following proxy, motivated by Lemma 7:

$$\min_{p \in c(\mathcal{D}^+)} \left\{ \hat{g}(p) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \max_{i \in [m]} \langle A_i, p \rangle \right\}. \quad (\text{1FPD-Proxy})$$

By Lemma 7, the optimizer of this problem must be p^{λ^*} . Note $\hat{g}(p^{\lambda^*}) = 1$ so we want a p such that $\hat{g}(p) \leq 1 + \varepsilon/n$. We solve this as an approximate feasibility problem in a packing LP by using the PST framework over $c(\mathcal{D}^+)$, which is convex, according to the following lemma.

Lemma 8 *Let $p^{(1)}, \dots, p^{(k)}$ be points in $c(\mathcal{D})$, and let $\zeta \in \Delta^k$ be coefficients. Then, we have $c(\zeta_1 c^{-1}(p^{(1)}) + \dots + \zeta_k c^{-1}(p^{(k)})) \leq \zeta_1 p^{(1)} + \dots + \zeta_k p^{(k)}$. Consequently, $c(\mathcal{D}^+)$ is convex.*

Proof Let us look at one coordinate $i \in [n]$. By the weighted harmonic-arithmetic inequality:

$$\begin{aligned} c(\zeta_1 c^{-1}(p^{(1)}) + \dots + \zeta_k c^{-1}(p^{(k)}))_i &= \left(\zeta_1 \frac{1}{p_i^{(1)}} + \dots + \zeta_k \frac{1}{p_i^{(k)}} \right)^{-1} \\ &\leq \zeta_1 p_i^{(1)} + \dots + \zeta_k p_i^{(k)} = \left(\zeta_1 p^{(1)} + \dots + \zeta_k p^{(k)} \right)_i. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Now we prove convexity of $c(\mathcal{D}^+)$. Let $q^{(1)}, \dots, q^{(k)} \in c(\mathcal{D}^+)$. Since every constraint in \mathcal{D}^+ is coordinate-wise smaller than some constraint in \mathcal{D} , it follows that every point $q^{(j)} \in c(\mathcal{D}^+)$ is coordinate-wise larger than some point $p^{(j)} \in c(\mathcal{D})$, that is $q^{(j)} \geq p^{(j)}$ for $j \in [k]$. Thus we obtain

$$\sum_{j \in [k]} \zeta_j q^{(j)} \geq \sum_{j \in [k]} \zeta_j p^{(j)} \stackrel{\textcircled{1}}{\geq} c \left(\sum_{j \in [k]} \zeta_j c(p^{(j)}) \right) \stackrel{\textcircled{2}}{\in} c(\mathcal{D}).$$

Inequality $\textcircled{1}$ is the first part of the lemma above, and the membership $\textcircled{2}$ is due to the convexity of \mathcal{D} , which is a polytope. The constraints in $c(\mathcal{D}^+)$ are exactly the ones that are coordinate-wise greater than some constraint in $c(\mathcal{D})$, so we have $\sum_{j \in [k]} \zeta_j q_j \in c(\mathcal{D}^+)$. \blacksquare

Figure 2: Left, the dual polytope \mathcal{D}^+ containing \mathcal{D} . The centroid $c(\cdot)$ maps dual points (i.e., constraints) to primal points. Right, \mathcal{P} and the image of \mathcal{D} and \mathcal{D}^+ via c . Note $c(\mathcal{D}^+) \cap \mathcal{P}$ is exactly one point, which is also contained in $c(\mathcal{D})$. And note $c(\mathcal{D})$ can be non-convex, but $c(\mathcal{D}^+)$ is convex.

3.2. The PST algorithm

Plotkin, Shmoys, and Tardos designed a framework (PST) for solving LP (PST95). This result was improved by (AHK12) for the case of packing and covering LP. We can use this framework to solve Problem (1FPD-Proxy) if we can provide a good feasibility oracle, as explained in the sequel. The PST framework focuses on checking the feasibility of $Ap \leq \mathbb{1}_m$, with p in a convex set \mathcal{X} . Then, it obtains either a certificate of infeasibility of the problem or computes a point $p \in \mathcal{X}$ such that $Ap \leq (1 + \varepsilon)\mathbb{1}_m$, for some given $\varepsilon > 0$. The PST framework works by calling an oracle which solves the simpler feasibility problem of finding

$$p \in \mathcal{X} \text{ such that } \langle A^T \Lambda, p \rangle \leq 1, \quad (12)$$

for some distribution $\Lambda \in \Delta^m$. That is, given a single constraint h^Λ , written as a convex combination of the constraints defined by A , the query asks for a point $p \in \mathcal{X}$ that satisfies the constraint. In our case, we apply the framework to $\mathcal{X} = c(\mathcal{D}^+)$ to find a point $p \in c(\mathcal{D}^+)$ with $Ap \leq (1 + \varepsilon)\mathbb{1}_m$. We can apply PST because $c(\mathcal{D}^+)$ is convex. Our oracle subproblems are always solvable because $p^{\lambda^*} \in \mathcal{P}$ satisfies them all. We use the following formulation of the PST and multiplicative weights (MW) algorithms for packing LP, which is a slight variation of (AHK12). The MW algorithm and its guarantees are presented in Lemma 15.

Lemma 9 (PST guarantee) \Downarrow *Let $\sigma, \tau \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$. For a target accuracy $\varepsilon \in (0, 4 \min\{\sigma, \tau\}]$, run the MW algorithm of Lemma 15 with $\delta = \varepsilon/2$, losses $\ell^{(k)} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathbb{1}_m - Ap^{(k)}$ assumed to be in $[-\sigma, \tau]^m$, where $p^{(k)}$ is the point the oracle outputs at iteration k when the constraint that is queried is given by $A^T(\Lambda^{(k)} / \|\Lambda^{(k)}\|_1)$, and where $\Lambda^{(k)}$ are the weights computed by the MW algorithm. Then, after $K = \frac{32\sigma\tau \log(m)}{\varepsilon^2}$ iterations, we obtain a solution $\bar{p} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K p^{(k)}$ that satisfies $\hat{g}(\bar{p}) \leq 1 + \varepsilon$.*

In order to give a solution of Problem (1FP-Dual), we are also interested in recovering some $\lambda \in \Delta^m$ such that $\hat{g}(p^\lambda)$ is small. Assume the oracle returns a point $p^{(k)} = p^{\lambda^{(k)}}$ for some $\lambda^{(k)}$ it

can also provide. Then, even if $\bar{p} \in \mathcal{D}^+ \setminus \mathcal{D}$, we have by [Lemma 8](#) that $\bar{\lambda} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \lambda^{(k)}$ defines a point $p^{\bar{\lambda}} \in \mathcal{D}$ such that $p^{\bar{\lambda}} \leq \bar{p}$. Hence $\hat{g}(p^{\bar{\lambda}}) \leq \hat{g}(\bar{p}) \leq 1 + \varepsilon$, so $\bar{\lambda}$ can be used as our dual solution.

Thus our task is to construct an oracle with good enough σ and τ , which are called the width parameters of the oracle. We also need to make sure that $\varepsilon \leq 4 \min\{\sigma, \tau\}$, and that we can output a point p^λ in \mathcal{D} , and a corresponding λ . Regardless, this algorithm runs in $\tilde{O}(\sigma\tau/\varepsilon^2)$ iterations, which is slower than what we aim for, for constant σ and τ . Our approach to obtain a fast algorithm is to design an adaptive feasibility oracle. We provide our best solution $\bar{\lambda}^{(t)}$ to the oracle, which satisfies $\hat{g}(p^{\bar{\lambda}^{(t)}}) \leq 1 + \delta$, for some $\delta > 0$. Given such a δ -approximate solution we identify a set of indices $I_t \subseteq [n]$ such that the constraints $\{A_i, i \notin I_t\}$ are redundant, in the sense that the oracle is guaranteed to return points satisfying them even if they are removed from the problem. We remove these constraints since they would yield large values of τ . Hence, we can run our MW algorithm with the remaining $|I_t|$ constraints. Denote A_{I_t} the matrix that has $\{A_i : i \in I_t\}$ as rows, in increasing order of i . In this case if $\Lambda \in \Delta^{|I_t|}$, we denote $h^\Lambda = A_{I_t}^T \Lambda$ and $p^\Lambda = c(A_{I_t}^T \Lambda)$ accordingly. Our oracle, when given a query h^Λ , uses both constraints h^Λ and $h^{\bar{\lambda}^{(t)}}$ to return a point p satisfying the oracle condition (12) and such that the loss $\mathbb{1}_{|I_t|} - A_{I_t} p$ is in $[-\sigma_\delta, \tau_\delta]^{|I_t|}$, with

$$\sigma_\delta \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \begin{cases} \sqrt{2\delta n} + 2\delta n & \text{if } \delta \leq 2 \\ \frac{1+2\delta}{1+\delta} \max_{i \in [n]} \{1/h_i^{\bar{\lambda}^{(t)}}\} - 1 & \text{if } \delta > 2 \end{cases}, \quad \tau_\delta \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \min\{3\sqrt{2\delta n}, 1\}. \quad (13)$$

In fact, σ_δ can be defined as the minimum of its two expressions above, regardless of the value of δ . But we shall use this definition for our algorithm. In the next section, we present the construction and analysis of such an oracle and the set I_t . We observe that, because the parameters depend on δ , we can restart the MW algorithm, and run it in several stages, indexed by $t = 0, \dots, T$. This allows for incrementally reducing the width parameters and obtaining a better overall complexity, as we prove in the following theorem.

Algorithm 2 Optimization of the dual of 1-fair packing with oracle \mathfrak{D}

Input: Matrix $A \in \mathcal{M}_{m \times n}(\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0})$ normalized as in (1). Accuracy $\varepsilon \in (0, (n-1)n]$.

- 1: $\bar{\lambda}^{(0)} \leftarrow \text{concat}(\mathbb{1}_n/n, \mathbb{0}_{m-n}) \in \Delta^m$; $\varepsilon_{-1} = n - 1$ $\diamond p^{\bar{\lambda}^{(0)}}$ is an ε_{-1} -minimizer of \hat{g}

- 2: **for** $t = 0$ **to** $T \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \max\{0, \lceil \log_2(2/(\varepsilon/n)) \rceil\}$ **do**
- 3: $I_t \leftarrow \{i \in [m] : \langle A_i, p^{\bar{\lambda}^{(t)}} \rangle \geq \frac{1+\varepsilon_{t-1}}{1+2\varepsilon_{t-1}n+\sqrt{2\varepsilon_{t-1}n}}\}$ \diamond Remove redundant constraints
- 4: **if** t **is** 0 **then** $\varepsilon_t \leftarrow \max\{2, \varepsilon/n\}$ **else** $\varepsilon_t \leftarrow \varepsilon_{t-1}/2$ \diamond Next target accuracy
- 5: $\Lambda^{(1)} \leftarrow \mathbb{1}_{|I_t|}$ \diamond Restart MW
- 6: **for** $k = 1$ **to** $K_t \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} 32\tau_{\varepsilon_{t-1}}\sigma_{\varepsilon_{t-1}} \log(|I_t|)/\varepsilon_t^2 = \tilde{O}(n/\varepsilon_t)$ **do**
- 7: $\lambda^{(k)}, p^{\lambda^{(k)}} \leftarrow \mathfrak{D}(\text{query } \Lambda^{(k)} / \|\Lambda^{(k)}\|_1, \text{ current solution } \bar{\lambda}^{(t)}, \text{ index set } I_t) \in (\Delta^m, c(\mathcal{D}))$
- 8: $\ell^{(k)} \leftarrow \mathbb{1}_{|I_t|} - A_{I_t} p^{\lambda^{(k)}}$
- 9: $\Lambda^{(k+1)} \leftarrow \Lambda^{(k)} \odot (\mathbb{1}_{|I_t|} - (\varepsilon_t / (4\tau_{\varepsilon_{t-1}}\sigma_{\varepsilon_{t-1}})) \cdot \ell^{(k)})$ \diamond MW step
- 10: **end for**
- 11: $\bar{\lambda}^{(t+1)} \leftarrow \frac{1}{K_t} \sum_{k=1}^{K_t} \lambda^{(k)}$
- 12: **end for**
- 13: **return** $\bar{\lambda} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \bar{\lambda}^{(T+1)}$

Output: $A p^{\bar{\lambda}} \leq (1 + \varepsilon/n) \mathbb{1}_m$, that is, $\hat{g}(p^{\bar{\lambda}}) \leq 1 + \varepsilon/n$. Hence $g(\bar{\lambda}) - g(\lambda^*) \leq \varepsilon$.

Theorem 10 *Let $\varepsilon \in (0, n(n-1)]$. Suppose we have a feasibility oracle \mathfrak{D} satisfying (12) and (13), when we filter constraints according to Algorithm 2. Then, Algorithm 2 computes, in $\tilde{O}(n^2/\varepsilon)$ iterations, a point $\bar{\lambda}$ which is an ε -minimizer of g . Moreover, $p^{\bar{\lambda}}$ is an (ε/n) -minimizer of \hat{g} .*

Proof Our aim is to use the PST framework to obtain a $\hat{\lambda} \in \Delta^m$ such that $p^{\hat{\lambda}}$ is an (ε/n) -minimizer of \hat{g} so that we can use Lemma 7 to conclude $\hat{\lambda}$ is an ε -minimizer of g . We will run the MW algorithm several times, restarting the weights between executions. Let $\varepsilon_t \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} 2^{1-t}$ for $t \geq 0$. At phase t , we aim to obtain a dual point $\bar{\lambda}^{(t+1)}$ such that $p^{\bar{\lambda}^{(t+1)}}$ is an ε_t -minimizer of \hat{g} . So we first aim for a 2-minimizer and then we halve the accuracy sequentially. The initial point is $\bar{\lambda}^{(0)} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \text{concat}(\mathbb{1}_n/n, \mathbb{0}_{m-n})$, where concat is defined as the concatenation of vectors, so that $\bar{\lambda}^{(0)} = (\frac{1}{n}, \dots, \frac{1}{n}, 0, \dots, 0) \in \Delta^m$, with n entries with value $\frac{1}{n}$. This point satisfies that $h^{\bar{\lambda}^{(0)}} = \mathbb{1}_n/n$ and $p^{\bar{\lambda}^{(0)}} = \mathbb{1}_n$, since we assumed $x_i \leq 1$ are the first n constraints of A , i.e., the first n rows of A are e_i for $i \in [n]$. Because the maximum entry of A is 1, we have $\hat{g}(p^{\bar{\lambda}^{(0)}}) \leq n$, i.e., $p^{\bar{\lambda}^{(0)}}$ is an $(n-1)$ -minimizer of \hat{g} . Hence we denote $\varepsilon_{-1} = n-1$ for convenience.

So for $t = 0$, the first phase, we seek to find a 2-minimizer of \hat{g} . Thus, this is the only phase in which we use the second case of the value of σ_δ , cf. (13). We have $\tau_{\varepsilon_{-1}} = 1$ and $\sigma_{\varepsilon_{-1}} = 2n-2$ and $4 \min\{\tau_{\varepsilon_{-1}}, \sigma_{\varepsilon_{-1}}\} = 4$. Note that if $\varepsilon/n \geq 2$, we can actually stop earlier so T in the algorithm is 0, there is only one phase, and ε_0 is actually set to ε/n . At this phase our *good previous solution* is the initial point $\bar{\lambda}^{(0)}$. Assume first $\varepsilon_0 = 2$. The condition $2 = \varepsilon_0 \leq 4 \min\{\tau_{\varepsilon_{-1}}, \sigma_{\varepsilon_{-1}}\} = 4$ is satisfied. Thus, according to Lemma 9, we reach the ε_0 -minimizer after $K_0 = \tilde{O}(\frac{n}{\varepsilon_0^2}) = \tilde{O}(n)$ iterations. If ε_0 is $\varepsilon/n > 2$, we can artificially set $\tau_{\varepsilon_{-1}}$ to a larger value, say ε/n , so that the condition $\varepsilon_0 \leq 4 \min\{\tau_{\varepsilon_{-1}}, \sigma_{\varepsilon_{-1}}\} = 4\tau_{\varepsilon_{-1}}$ trivially holds, and the complexity is $\tilde{O}(\frac{\varepsilon/n \cdot \sigma_{\varepsilon_{-1}}}{(\varepsilon/n)^2}) = \tilde{O}(\frac{n^2}{\varepsilon})$ iterations, which satisfies the theorem. In fact, for large ε , i.e., for $\varepsilon/n > 2$, just aiming for an $\hat{\varepsilon} = \exp(\varepsilon/n) - 1$ is significantly faster and enough. The latter is true according to Lemma 7 without bounding $\log(1 + \hat{\varepsilon}) \leq \hat{\varepsilon}$.

Now, if $T > 0$, we run several phases of the MW algorithm. Iteration $t > 0$ takes $K_t \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{32\tau_{\varepsilon_{t-1}}\sigma_{\varepsilon_{t-1}}\log(|I_t|)}{\varepsilon_t^2} = \tilde{O}(\frac{\tau_{\varepsilon_{t-1}}\sigma_{\varepsilon_{t-1}}}{\varepsilon_t^2})$ iterations by the PST guarantee, cf Lemma 9. If $\varepsilon_{t-1} > \frac{1}{n}$ we have $\tau_{\varepsilon_{t-1}} \cdot \sigma_{\varepsilon_{t-1}} = O(1 \cdot \varepsilon_{t-1}n)$ and if $\varepsilon_{t-1} \leq \frac{1}{n}$ we have $\tau_{\varepsilon_{t-1}} \cdot \sigma_{\varepsilon_{t-1}} = O(\sqrt{\varepsilon_{t-1}n} \cdot \sqrt{\varepsilon_{t-1}n})$. In any case, it is $K_t = \tilde{O}(\frac{n}{\varepsilon_t})$, as $\varepsilon_{t-1}/\varepsilon_t = 2 = O(1)$. The assumption $\varepsilon_t \leq 4 \min\{\sigma_{\varepsilon_{t-1}}, \tau_{\varepsilon_{t-1}}\}$ is satisfied in these phases. Indeed, if $\varepsilon_t \geq 1/n$, we have $\varepsilon_t < \varepsilon_0 = 2$ and $\sigma_{\varepsilon_{t-1}} \geq 1$, $\tau_{\varepsilon_{t-1}} = 1$. In the case $\varepsilon_t < 1/n$, we have $4 \min\{\tau_{\varepsilon_{t-1}}, \sigma_{\varepsilon_{t-1}}\} \geq \sqrt{\varepsilon_{t-1}n}$ which is $> \varepsilon_t$.

If $T = \lceil \log_2(2/(\varepsilon/n)) \rceil > 0$, then $\varepsilon_T \leq \varepsilon/n$ and the total number of iterations is

$$\sum_{t=0}^T K_t = \tilde{O}\left(\sum_{t=0}^T \frac{n}{\varepsilon_t}\right) = \tilde{O}\left(\sum_{t=0}^T n2^{t-1}\right) = \tilde{O}(n2^T) = \tilde{O}\left(\frac{n^2}{\varepsilon}\right).$$

The complexity of an iteration is $\tilde{O}(N)$, assuming $N \geq m$ (recall $m \geq n$ since we added the constraints $x_i \leq 1$). Indeed, computing I_t , Algorithm 2, and computing the constraints of the query $\Lambda^{(k)}/\|\Lambda^{(k)}\|_1$ and current solution $\bar{\lambda}^{(t)}$, to be used by the oracle, requires multiplying a vector by A or a subset of its rows, which is $O(N)$. The oracle query takes $\tilde{O}(n)$, and the rest of operations in Algorithm 2 are simple and take $O(m)$ time. Note the amortized complexity of Algorithm 2 is $O(m)$ per iteration. \blacksquare

3.3. The PST oracle and the redundant constraints

In order to give a fast solution for Problem (1FPD-Proxy), we want to design an adaptive oracle. That is, it should satisfy (12), and it should output better points if it already knows a good approximate solution. Generically, assume that the oracle has access to a feasible constraint $s \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} A^T \lambda^{(s)} \in \mathcal{D}$, with $\lambda^{(s)} \in \Delta^m$ satisfying $p^{\lambda^{(s)}} = c(s)$ is a point with $\hat{g}(p^{\lambda^{(s)}}) \leq 1 + \delta$. In other words, $c(s)$ is a δ -approximate solution to Problem (1FPD-Proxy). Let $q \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} A^T \lambda^{(q)} \in \mathcal{D}$, with $\lambda^{(q)} \in \Delta^m$ be a query constraint. In Algorithm 2, $\lambda^{(s)}$ and $\lambda^{(q)}$ correspond to $\bar{\lambda}^{(t)}$ and $\Lambda^{(k)} / \|\Lambda^{(k)}\|_1$ respectively, where the latter is interpreted as having coefficients equal to zero for constraints $i \notin I_t$.

Figure 3: The lens $\mathcal{L}_\delta(v)$ given by a feasible solution s , for $\omega = 1$. In the actual algorithm, we have $\omega > 1$, which defines a larger set in which the affine part is translated upwards.

The main geometric idea is that by using the solution s , we can define a region whose size depends on δ containing the optimum p^{λ^*} of Problem (1FPD-Proxy). We will guarantee the oracle returns points in this region, which in turn means that the oracle returns points close to the optimum. We call this geometric object the *lens of a point*:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\omega\delta}(v) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{x \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n : \langle c^{-1}(x), v \rangle \leq 1, \langle c^{-1}(v), x \rangle \leq 1 + \omega\delta\},$$

where $\omega \in (1, 2]$ is a parameter; we chose $\omega = 2$ in the algorithm. We depict the lens in Figure 3. We apply this definition to the point $v \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} c(s)/(1 + \delta)$, which is in \mathcal{P} because $\hat{g}(s) \leq 1 + \delta$ implies that $c(s)/(1 + \delta) \in \mathcal{P}$.

We show in Lemma 16 that, by using the bisection method, we can efficiently find a convex combination $(1 - \mu)s + \mu q$ that will result in a constraint, whose centroid is the point o we output. It satisfies the first oracle condition, and is in the lens. Also, we can recover $\lambda^{(o)}$ as $(1 - \mu)\lambda^{(s)} + \mu\lambda^{(q)}$.

If the oracle can output a point o in the lens, we will have low width parameters for the constraints A_i that do not cover the lens, as we show in Proposition 18. That is, for one such constraint A_i , the corresponding loss is $1 - \langle A_i, o \rangle \in [-\sigma, \tau]$. The other constraints could be problematic in terms of width parameters because $\langle A_i, o \rangle$ could be much smaller than 1, forcing τ to be large.

However, we do not need to optimize over these constraints because $\hat{g} \geq 1$, so these constraints do not contribute to the max in its definition. This leads to the set of non-redundant constraints I , which for efficiency reasons, we relax to those indices of constraints A_i that do not cover a box that contains the lens, cf. [Lemma 17](#). We prove this is good enough in terms of the width parameters. The computation of I , which is done before each restart phase, requires $O(N)$ operations and each query to the oracle takes $O(n \log(\frac{n}{(\omega-1)\delta} + \frac{n}{\omega-1}))$ operations, cf. [Lemma 16](#).

Algorithm 3 Feasibility oracle \mathfrak{D}

Input: An approximate solution $s \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} A^T \lambda^{(s)}$, $\lambda^{(s)} \in \Delta^m$, $\hat{g}(c(s)) \leq 1 + \delta$. Query constraint $q = A^T \lambda^{(q)}$, $\lambda^{(q)} \in \Delta^m$. Precision parameter $1 < \omega \leq 2$, default value $\omega = 2$. Index set of non-redundant constraints $I = \{i \in [m] : \langle A_i, c(s) \rangle \geq \frac{1+\delta}{1+\omega\delta n + \sqrt{\omega\delta n}}\}$.

Output: $\lambda^{(o)} \in \Delta^m$ and point $o \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} c(A^T \lambda^{(o)}) \in c(\mathcal{D})$ such that

1. o is covered by q , i.e., $\langle q, o \rangle \leq 1$.
2. If $i \in I$ then $\langle A_i, o \rangle \in [1-\tau, 1+\sigma]$ where $\sigma = \min(\sqrt{\omega\delta n} + \omega\delta n, \frac{1+\omega\delta}{1+\delta} \max_{i \in [n]} s_i^{-1} - 1)$, $\tau = \min(3\sqrt{\omega\delta n}, 1)$.
3. It satisfies all redundant constraints, i.e., $\langle A_i, o \rangle \leq 1$, if $i \in [m] \setminus I$.

-
- 1: **if** $\langle s, c(q) \rangle \leq \frac{1+\omega\delta}{1+\delta}$ **then return** $\lambda^{(o)} = \lambda^{(q)}$, $o = c(q)$
 - 2: **else if** $\langle q, c(s) \rangle \leq 1$ **then return** $\lambda^{(o)} = \lambda^{(s)}$, $o = c(s)$
 - 3: **else** Find $\mu \in (0, 1)$ s.t. $\langle s, c((1-\mu)s + \mu q) \rangle \in (1, \frac{1+\omega\delta}{1+\delta})$ via the bisection method
 - 4: **end if**
 - 5: **return** $\lambda^{(o)} = (1-\mu)\lambda^{(s)} + \mu\lambda^{(q)}$, $o = c((1-\mu)s + \mu q)$
-

3.4. An application to the Yamnitsky-Levin algorithm via 1FP-Dual

The Yamnitsky-Levin algorithm (YL), or method of simplices ([YL82](#)), belongs to a family of LP algorithms that bound the feasible region by a geometric shape that is progressively decreased in volume, in order to solve the feasibility problem, using which one can solve LP. ([Lev65](#)) proposed the method of centralized splitting as a way to solve the linear feasibility problem. It starts with a simplex bounding the feasible region P that is sequentially intersected with several halfspaces containing P . Then, it re-encloses the remaining polyhedron by a simplex that is smaller in volume. This algorithm later inspired the ellipsoid algorithm ([YN76](#)), that only needed the intersection with one halfspace. Later ([YL82](#)) proved that their method of simplices, which is a variant of the algorithm in ([Lev65](#)), can use only one intersection per iteration, and solves LP in weakly polynomial time. In particular, the YL algorithm computes the centroid $c^{(k)}$ of the current bounding simplex $\Delta^{(k)}$ at each iteration, and chooses an arbitrary constraint $h^{(k)}$ of the LP problem that does not cover $c^{(k)}$. The simplex $\Delta^{(k+1)}$ results from substituting the facet that opposes the vertex $v^{(k)}$ that is farthest from $h^{(k)}$, by a convex combination of this facet and $h^{(k)}$.

We note that since the YL algorithm chooses constraints arbitrarily, one can first consider the set of constraints \mathcal{H}_v whose normals are in the normal fan of any particular fixed vertex v , and one would optimize the volume of the simplex when the corner given by v is fixed. The YL algorithm would repeatedly run this procedure in stages, by pivoting to other vertices, until a feasible point is found or until the volume of the bounding simplex is small enough. In this case, a stage is equivalent

to **(IFP-Dual)**. One stage stops when all $h \in \mathcal{H}_v$ cover $c^{(k)}$, and this stopping condition is equivalent to reaching a $(1/n)$ -minimizer of **(IFPD-Proxy)**, for a matrix A depending on \mathcal{H}_v .

The classical analysis of the YL algorithm guarantees that a stage finishes after $\tilde{O}(Nn^3)$ operations if we start with a natural non-informed initial simplex. Our **Algorithm 2** achieves this accuracy after $\tilde{O}(Nn^2)$ operations. See **Appendix D** for the description and analysis of the YL stage.

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Appendix A. Missing proofs from Section 1

Lemma 11 Recall the definition of the primal problem (1FP):

$$\max_{x \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n} \left\{ f(x) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sum_{i=1}^n \log x_i : Ax \leq \mathbf{1}_m \right\}. \quad (1FP)$$

Then, its Lagrange dual can be formulated as:

$$\min_{\lambda \in \Delta^m} \left\{ g(\lambda) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} - \sum_{i=1}^n \log(A^T \lambda)_i - n \log n \right\}. \quad (1FP-Dual)$$

Where $\Delta^m \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^m : \sum \lambda_i = 1, \lambda \geq 0\}$ is the m -dimensional (probability) simplex.

Proof By definition of Lagrangian duality, the dual of (1FP) is

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{y \geq 0} \left\{ \max_{x \geq 0} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n \log(x_i) - y^T (Ax - \mathbf{1}_m) \right\} \right\} = \\ & \min_{y \geq 0} \left\{ \langle y, \mathbf{1}_m \rangle + \max_{x \geq 0} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n (\log(x_i) - (y^T A)_i x_i) \right\} \right\} \end{aligned}$$

We can explicitly compute the x_i variables by differentiation, to obtain $x_i = (y^T A)_i^{-1}$. Thus the problem is equivalent to:

$$\min_{y \geq 0} \left\{ \langle y, \mathbf{1}_m \rangle + \sum_{i=1}^n (-\log(y^T A)_i - 1) \right\}.$$

Now, let $\lambda = \frac{1}{\langle y, \mathbf{1}_m \rangle} y$ and $t = \langle y, \mathbf{1}_m \rangle$. Then, $y = t\lambda$ with $\lambda \in \Delta^m$ and we write the problem as:

$$\min_{\lambda \in \Delta^m} \min_{t \geq 0} \left\{ t - \sum_{i=1}^n \log(\lambda^T A)_i - n \log t - n \right\}.$$

The value of t minimizing $t - n \log t$ is $t = n$ by differentiation so the problem reduces to

$$\min_{\lambda \in \Delta^m} \left\{ - \sum_{i=1}^n \log(A^T \lambda)_i - n \log n \right\}. \quad (14)$$

■

Appendix B. Missing proofs from Section 2

Proof of Proposition 1. Recall $\beta = \frac{\varepsilon}{6n \log(2mn^2/\varepsilon)}$ and that $\log(\cdot)$ is the natural logarithm. We will prove the proposition in three steps:

- 1) $\hat{f}(\hat{x}^*) - \hat{f}(x_r^*) \leq \hat{f}(\hat{x}^*) + f_r(x_r^*) \leq 3\varepsilon$.
- 2) The point x_r^ε satisfies $A \exp(x_r^\varepsilon) \leq (1 + \varepsilon/n)\mathbf{1}_m$.
- 3) The point $\hat{u} = x_r^\varepsilon - \log(1 + \varepsilon/n)\mathbf{1}_n$ satisfies $f(x^*) - f(u) \leq f(\exp(\hat{x}^*)) - f(\exp(\hat{u})) = \hat{f}(\hat{x}^*) - \hat{f}(\hat{u}) \leq 5\varepsilon$ and $A \exp(\hat{u}) \leq \mathbf{1}_m$.

For the first part, take the point $x = \log(1 - \varepsilon/n)\mathbf{1}_n + \hat{x}^* \in B$. It satisfies $A \exp(x) \leq (1 - \varepsilon/n)\mathbf{1}_m$, because \hat{x}^* is feasible. Thus

$$\frac{\beta}{1+\beta} \sum_{i=1}^m (A \exp(x))_i^{\frac{1+\beta}{\beta}} \leq m(1 - \varepsilon/n)^{1/\beta} \leq m \left(\frac{\varepsilon}{2mn^2} \right)^6 \leq \varepsilon. \quad (15)$$

We used $\frac{\beta}{1+\beta} \leq 1$, $\frac{1+\beta}{\beta} \geq \frac{1}{\beta}$, and $(1 - \varepsilon/n)^{\frac{n}{\varepsilon}} \leq e^{-1}$. Consequently, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{f}(\hat{x}^*) - \hat{f}(x_r^*) &\stackrel{\textcircled{1}}{\leq} \hat{f}(\hat{x}^*) + f_r(x_r^*) \stackrel{\textcircled{2}}{\leq} \hat{f}(\hat{x}^*) + f_r(x) \\ &= \langle \mathbf{1}_n, \hat{x}^* \rangle + \left(-\langle \mathbf{1}_n, \log(1 - \varepsilon/n)\mathbf{1}_n + \hat{x}^* \rangle + \frac{\beta}{1+\beta} \sum_{i=1}^m (A \exp(x))_i^{\frac{1+\beta}{\beta}} \right) \\ &\stackrel{\textcircled{3}}{\leq} n \log\left(\frac{1}{1 - \varepsilon/n}\right) + \varepsilon \stackrel{\textcircled{4}}{\leq} 3\varepsilon. \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Above, $\textcircled{1}$ is true by definition of f_r being $-\hat{f}$ plus a non-negative regularizer. The point x is in B and $x_r^* = \arg \min_{x \in B} \{f_r(x)\}$ so we have $\textcircled{2}$. Inequality $\textcircled{3}$ uses (15) and $\textcircled{4}$ uses $\log(x) \leq x - 1$ and $\varepsilon/n \leq 1/2$.

For the second part, suppose for the moment that there is some i such that $(A \exp(x_r^\varepsilon))_i > 1 + \varepsilon/n$. In that case

$$(A \exp(x_r^\varepsilon))_i^{\frac{1+\beta}{\beta}} \geq (1 + \varepsilon/n)^{(2n/\varepsilon) \cdot 3 \log(2mn^2/\varepsilon)} \geq \left(\frac{2mn^2}{\varepsilon} \right)^3,$$

since $(1 + \varepsilon/n)^{2n/\varepsilon} \geq e$ when $\varepsilon/n \leq 1/2$. We have $x_r^\varepsilon \in B$ so $f_r(x_r^\varepsilon) \geq -\langle \mathbf{1}_n, x_r^\varepsilon \rangle + \frac{\beta}{1+\beta} \left(\frac{2mn^2}{\varepsilon} \right)^3 \geq \frac{\beta}{2} \left(\frac{2mn^2}{\varepsilon} \right)^3$. On the other hand, it holds for the point $y = -\log(mn)\mathbf{1}_n$ that

$$\begin{aligned} f_r(y) &= n \log(mn) + \frac{\beta}{1+\beta} \sum_{i=1}^m (A \exp(y))_i^{\frac{1+\beta}{\beta}} \\ &\stackrel{\textcircled{1}}{\leq} n \log(mn) + m(1/m)^{\frac{1+\beta}{\beta}} \leq n \log(mn) + 1 \\ &\stackrel{\textcircled{2}}{<} \frac{\beta}{2} \left(\frac{2mn^2}{\varepsilon} \right)^3 - \varepsilon < f_r(x_r^\varepsilon) - \varepsilon, \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

contradicting the assumption $f_r(x_r^\varepsilon) - f_r(x_r^*) \leq \varepsilon$, as we would obtain $\varepsilon < f_r(x_r^\varepsilon) - f_r(y) \leq f_r(x_r^\varepsilon) - f_r(x_r^*)$, since $y \in B$. So it must be $(A \exp(x_r^\varepsilon))_i \leq 1 + \varepsilon/n$. Inequality ① uses that the maximum entry of A is 1, and $\frac{\beta}{1+\beta} \leq 1$. One can show ② by proving the stronger inequality that results from substituting β by $\varepsilon/(6n \cdot 2mn^2/\varepsilon)$, which is a lower value. Computing derivatives in both sides shows that this inequality holds if it does for $m = 1$ and $\varepsilon = \frac{n}{2}$, and the latter is easy to check.

For the third part, we have $A \exp(\hat{u}) = A \frac{\exp(x_r^\varepsilon)}{1+\varepsilon/n} \leq \mathbf{1}_m$. And finally, putting all together we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{f}(\hat{x}^*) - \hat{f}(\hat{u}) &= \hat{f}(\hat{x}^*) - \hat{f}(x_r^\varepsilon) + n \log(1 + \varepsilon/n) \\ &\leq \hat{f}(\hat{x}^*) + f_r(x_r^\varepsilon) + n \log(1 + \varepsilon/n) \\ &\leq \hat{f}(\hat{x}^*) + f_r(x_r^*) + \varepsilon + n \log(1 + \varepsilon/n) \\ &\leq 4\varepsilon + n \log(1 + \varepsilon/n) \leq 5\varepsilon. \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

■

Lemma 12 *Let A satisfy the normalization in (1), and let x^* be the optimizer of Problem (1FP). Then $x_i^* \geq 1/n$, for all $i \in [n]$.*

We now present the proof of Lemma 2, which guarantees the iterates of Algorithm 1 remain in the box B .

Proof of Lemma 2. For all $k \geq 0$, we have $z^{(k)} \in B$ by definition. If we have that $y^{(k-1)} \in B$, then $x^{(k)} \in B$ since $x^{(k)}$ is a convex combination of $y^{(k-1)}$ and $z^{(k-1)}$. So we only have to prove that for all $k \geq 0$, we have $y^{(k)} \in B$. We prove by induction that, for $k \geq 1$, it holds that $y^{(k)}$ is a convex combination of $\{z^{(i)}\}_{i=0}^k$ and that the weight of $z^{(k)}$ in this convex combination is $\frac{1}{\eta_k L}$. Firstly, we have $y^{(1)} = (1 - \frac{1}{\eta_1 L})z^{(0)} + \frac{1}{\eta_1 L}z^{(1)}$ (recall $x^{(0)} = z^{(0)}$). Now assuming our property holds up to $k-1$, use the definition of $y^{(k)}$ and $x^{(k)}$, to compute $y^{(k)} = \tau z^{(k-1)} + (1 - \tau)y^{(k-1)} + \frac{1}{\eta_k L}(z^{(k)} - z^{(k-1)})$. This is an affine combination of the $z^{(i)}$'s, by induction hypothesis. Moreover, the weights add up to $1 = \tau + (1 - \tau) + \frac{1}{\eta_k L} - \frac{1}{\eta_k L}$, and the weight on $z^{(k)}$ is $\frac{1}{\eta_k L}$. So we only have to prove the weight on $z^{(k-1)}$ is ≥ 0 in order to show that we indeed have a convex combination and not just an affine one. By induction hypothesis, we know the weight on $z^{(k-1)}$ coming from $y^{(k-1)}$ is $\frac{1}{\eta_{k-1} L}$. Hence, the weight on $z^{(k-1)}$ is $\tau + (1 - \tau)\frac{1}{\eta_{k-1} L} - \frac{1}{\eta_k L} = \tau > 0$, where the equality uses the definition of η_k . ■

Proof The normalization ensures that e_i are feasible points, for $i \in [n]$. That is, $Ae_i \leq \mathbf{1}_m$ because each $A_{ij} \leq 1$. Since x^* is the maximizer of Problem (1FP), by the first order optimality condition we have $\langle \nabla f(x^*), x - x^* \rangle \leq 0$, for any feasible point x . Suppose there is a coordinate $i \in [n]$ such that $x_i^* < \frac{1}{n}$. Then, $\langle \nabla f(x^*), e_i - x^* \rangle = \frac{1}{x_i^*} - \sum_{j=1}^n x_j^*/x_j^* > 0$, which is a contradiction. ■

Lemma 13 (Mirror Descent Lemma) *Let $\mathcal{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ be a closed convex set and let $\psi : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a 1-strongly convex map with respect to $\|\cdot\|$. Let $\|\cdot\|_*$ be the dual norm to $\|\cdot\|$ and let $\ell^{(k)} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ be an arbitrary loss vector. Given $z^{(k-1)} \in \mathcal{X}$, let $z^{(k)} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \arg \min_{z \in \mathcal{X}} \{D_\psi(z, z^{(k-1)}) + \eta \langle \ell^{(k)}, z \rangle\}$. Then, for all $u \in \mathcal{X}$ we have*

- a) $\eta \langle \ell^{(k)}, z^{(k-1)} - u \rangle \leq \frac{\eta^2}{2} \|\ell^{(k)}\|_*^2 + D_\psi(u, z^{(k-1)}) - D_\psi(u, z^{(k)})$.
- b) $\eta \langle \ell^{(k)}, z^{(k-1)} - u \rangle \leq \eta \langle \ell^{(k)}, z^{(k-1)} - z^{(k)} \rangle + D_\psi(u, z^{(k-1)}) - D_\psi(u, z^{(k)})$.

Proof We note that, by definition, we have $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} D_\psi(x, y) = \nabla \psi(x) - \nabla \psi(y)$. The lemma is due to

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \eta \ell^{(k)}, z^{(k-1)} - u \rangle &= \langle \eta \ell^{(k)}, z^{(k-1)} - z^{(k)} \rangle + \langle \eta \ell^{(k)}, z^{(k)} - u \rangle \\ &\stackrel{\textcircled{1}}{\leq} \langle \eta \ell^{(k)}, z^{(k-1)} - z^{(k)} \rangle - \langle \nabla \psi(z^{(k)}) - \nabla \psi(z^{(k-1)}), z^{(k)} - u \rangle \\ &\stackrel{\textcircled{2}}{=} \langle \eta \ell^{(k)}, z^{(k-1)} - z^{(k)} \rangle - D_\psi(z^{(k)}, z^{(k-1)}) + D_\psi(u, z^{(k-1)}) - D_\psi(u, z^{(k)}) \\ &\stackrel{\textcircled{3}}{\leq} \frac{\eta^2}{2} \|\ell^{(k)}\|_*^2 + D_\psi(u, z^{(k-1)}) - D_\psi(u, z^{(k)}). \end{aligned}$$

Inequality $\textcircled{1}$ comes from the first-order optimality condition of the definition of $z^{(k)}$, that is, $\langle \nabla \psi(z^{(k)}) - \nabla \psi(z^{(k-1)}) + \eta \ell^{(k)}, u - z^{(k)} \rangle \geq 0$ for all $u \in \mathcal{X}$. $\textcircled{2}$ is the triangle equality of Bregman divergences, and can be easily checked by using the definition.

If we drop the term $-D_\psi(z^{(k)}, z^{(k-1)})$ after $\textcircled{2}$, we obtain part b) of this lemma. $\textcircled{3}$ leads to part a), which is the classical mirror descent lemma. It uses the bound $D_\psi(z^{(k)}, z^{(k-1)}) \geq \frac{1}{2} \|z^{(k)} - z^{(k-1)}\|^2$, which holds due to the strong convexity of ψ . And then we applied the inequality $\langle v, w \rangle - \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 \leq \frac{1}{2} \|v\|_*^2$ for $v, w \in \mathbb{R}^n$, that holds by Cauchy-Schwarz and $\|v\|_* \cdot \|w\| \leq \frac{1}{2} \|v\|_*^2 + \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2$. ■

In the next lemma, we prove a crucial generalization of (DFO20, Lemma 3.1), which allows for showing our descent [Lemma 4](#).

Lemma 14 *Let $c \in [-1, 1]^n$ and let $\Delta \in \mathbb{R}^n$ be defined as $\Delta_j = -\frac{c_j \beta}{4(1+\beta)} \overline{\nabla_j f_r}(x)$, for $j \in [n]$. Then*

$$f_r(x + \Delta) - f_r(x) \leq \sum_{j=1}^n \left(1 - \frac{c_j}{2}\right) \Delta_j \nabla_j f_r(x).$$

Proof By using a Taylor expansion, there is a $t \in [0, 1]$ such that

$$f_r(x + \Delta) - f_r(x) = \langle \nabla f_r(x), \Delta \rangle + \frac{1}{2} \Delta^\top \nabla^2 f_r(x + t\Delta) \Delta. \quad (19)$$

The gradient and Hessian of f_r are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_j f_r(x) &= -1 + \sum_{i=1}^m (A \exp(x))_i^{\frac{1}{\beta}} a_{ij} \exp(x_j), \\ \nabla_{jk}^2 f_r(x) &= \mathbf{1}_{\{j=k\}} \sum_{i=1}^m (A \exp(x))_i^{\frac{1}{\beta}} a_{ij} \exp(x_j) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{i=1}^m (A \exp(x))_i^{\frac{1}{\beta}-1} a_{ij} \exp(x_j) a_{ik} \exp(x_k). \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

In order to control how much the function changes, we will require

$$\frac{1}{2}\nabla_{jk}^2 f_r(x) \leq \nabla_{jk}^2 f_r(x + t\Delta) \leq 2\nabla_{jk}^2 f_r(x).$$

We can guarantee the inequality on the right if we guarantee that each summand in the expression above does not grow by more than a factor of 2, and respectively the one on the left if each summand does not decrease by more than a factor of 2. Let $\Delta_{\max} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \max_{i \in [n]} \{\Delta_i\}$ and $\Delta_{\min} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \min_{i \in [n]} \{\Delta_i\}$. It suffices to have $\exp(\Delta_{\max})^{\frac{1}{\beta}+1} \leq 2$ and $\exp(\Delta_{\min})^{\frac{1}{\beta}+1} \geq 1/2$. Hence, it suffices to have for all $j \in [n]$, the following:

$$-\frac{\ln 2}{1 + \frac{1}{\beta}} \leq \Delta_j \leq \frac{\ln 2}{1 + \frac{1}{\beta}}. \quad (21)$$

In fact, we will use $\Delta_j = -\frac{c_j}{4} \cdot \frac{\beta}{1+\beta} \overline{\nabla_j f_r}(x)$ for all $j \in [n]$, which satisfy the condition since $|c_j \overline{\nabla_j f_r}(x)| \leq 1$. In such a case, by using the function $\text{sign}(x) = 1$ if $x \geq 0$ and -1 otherwise, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2}\Delta^\top \nabla^2 f_r(x + t\Delta)\Delta &\stackrel{\textcircled{1}}{\leq} \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{i=1}^m (A \exp(x))_i^{\frac{1}{\beta}} \Delta_j^2 a_{ij} \exp(x_j) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2\beta} \sum_{i=1}^m (A \exp(x))_i^{\frac{1}{\beta}-1} \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^n \Delta_j \Delta_k a_{ij} a_{ik} \exp(x_j) \exp(x_k) 2^{\text{sign}(\Delta_j \Delta_k)} \\ &\stackrel{\textcircled{2}}{\leq} \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{i=1}^m (A \exp(x))_i^{\frac{1}{\beta}} \Delta_j^2 a_{ij} \exp(x_j) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2\beta} \sum_{i=1}^m (A \exp(x))_i^{\frac{1}{\beta}-1} \sum_{j=1}^n \Delta_j^2 a_{ij} \exp(x_j) \cdot \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^n a_{ij} a_{ik} \exp(x_j) \exp(x_k) 4^{\text{sign}(\Delta_j \Delta_k)}} \\ &\stackrel{\textcircled{3}}{\leq} \frac{\beta+1}{\beta} \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{i=1}^m (A \exp(x))_i^{\frac{1}{\beta}} \Delta_j^2 a_{ij} \exp(x_j) \\ &\stackrel{\textcircled{4}}{=} \frac{\beta+1}{\beta} \sum_{j=1}^n \Delta_j^2 (\nabla_j f_r(x) + 1) \\ &\stackrel{\textcircled{5}}{=} \sum_{j=1}^n -\frac{c_j}{4} \Delta_j \overline{\nabla_j f_r}(x) (\nabla_j f_r(x) + 1) \\ &\stackrel{\textcircled{6}}{\leq} -\sum_{j=1}^n \frac{c_j}{2} \Delta_j \nabla_j f_r(x). \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

We used the inequalities $\nabla_{jk}^2 f_r(x + t\Delta) \leq 2\nabla_{jk}^2 f_r(x)$ and $-\nabla_{jk}^2 f_r(x + t\Delta) \leq -2^{-1}\nabla_{jk}^2 f_r(x)$ in

①. We used Cauchy-Schwarz in ② with the n^2 -dimensional vectors

$$(\Delta_j \Delta_k \sqrt{a_{ij} a_{ik} \exp(x_j) \exp(x_k)})_{j,k \in [n]} \quad \text{and} \quad (2^{\text{sign}(\Delta_j \Delta_k)} \sqrt{a_{ij} a_{ik} \exp(x_j) \exp(x_k)})_{j,k \in [n]},$$

in order to bound the last factor, so that the two first lines of the right hand side become proportional after bounding $4^{\text{sign}(\Delta_j \Delta_k)} \leq 4$ in (3). In (3), we also grouped these terms. In (4), we used the definition of the gradient. In (5), we used the value of Δ . Finally, (6) is a direct consequence of the truncated gradient definition (one can check the inequality for the three cases in $\nabla_j f_r(x) \in \{-1, 0, [0, 1], (1, \infty)\}$, while taking into account the sign of Δ_j).

Now, substituting into (19) we obtain:

$$f_r(x + \Delta) - f_r(x) \leq \sum_{j=1}^n \left(1 - \frac{c_j}{2}\right) \Delta_j \nabla_j f_r(x).$$

■

Proof of Lemma 5. It is enough to show that for all $i \in [n]$ we have

$$\eta_k \nu_i^{(k)} (z_i^{(k-1)} - u_i) + \eta_k^2 L \overline{\nabla_i f_r}(x^{(k)}) (x_i^{(k)} - y_i^{(k)}) \leq \frac{3}{2} \eta_k L \nabla_i f_r(x^{(k)}) (x_i^{(k)} - y_i^{(k)}) \quad (23)$$

because then we can conclude with

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \eta_k \nu_i^{(k)}, z^{(k-1)} - u \rangle + \eta_k^2 L \langle \overline{\nabla f_r}(x^{(k)}), x^{(k)} - y^{(k)} \rangle &\stackrel{\textcircled{1}}{\leq} \frac{3}{2} \eta_k L \langle \nabla f_r(x^{(k)}), x^{(k)} - y^{(k)} \rangle \\ &\stackrel{\textcircled{2}}{\leq} 3 \eta_k L (f_r(x^{(k)}) - f_r(y^{(k)})), \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

by adding up (23) in (1) and Lemma 4 in (2). In the analysis of (23) we exploit the simple but crucial fact that is that the gradient step for each coordinate is independent of the gradient step of other coordinates, due to the constraint set being a box. We present the rest of the proof in three cases. In the cases below, we will use $\nabla_i f_r(x^{(k)}) (x_i^{(k)} - y_i^{(k)}) \geq 0$, cf. Lemma 4. And also the fact that $\eta_k \leq 1/4$, as we observe in (9).

- If $\nu_i^{(k)} = 0$ then $\overline{\nabla_i f_r}(x^{(k)}) = \nabla_i f_r(x^{(k)}) \in [-1, 1]$. In such a case, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_k \nu_i^{(k)} (z_i^{(k-1)} - u_i) + \eta_k^2 L \overline{\nabla_i f_r}(x^{(k)}) (x_i^{(k)} - y_i^{(k)}) &= \eta_k^2 L \nabla_i f_r(x^{(k)}) (x_i^{(k)} - y_i^{(k)}) \\ &\leq \frac{3}{2} \eta_k L \nabla_i f_r(x^{(k)}) (x_i^{(k)} - y_i^{(k)}). \end{aligned}$$

- If $\nu_i^{(k)} > 0$ and $z_i^{(k)} > -\omega$ then the mirror descent step did not need to project along coordinate i , and we have $z_i^{(k)} = z_i^{(k-1)} - \omega \eta_k$, and thus $y_i^{(k)} = x_i^{(k)} - \omega/L$. In this case

$$\begin{aligned} &\eta_k \nu_i^{(k)} (z_i^{(k-1)} - u_i) + \eta_k^2 L \overline{\nabla_i f_r}(x^{(k)}) (x_i^{(k)} - y_i^{(k)}) \\ &\stackrel{\textcircled{1}}{\leq} \eta_k \nabla_i f_r(x^{(k)}) \omega + \eta_k^2 L \nabla_i f_r(x^{(k)}) (x_i^{(k)} - y_i^{(k)}) \\ &= \eta_k L \nabla_i f_r(x^{(k)}) (x_i^{(k)} - y_i^{(k)}) + \eta_k^2 L \nabla_i f_r(x^{(k)}) (x_i^{(k)} - y_i^{(k)}) \\ &\leq \frac{3}{2} \eta_k L \nabla_i f_r(x^{(k)}) (x_i^{(k)} - y_i^{(k)}). \end{aligned}$$

Above, we obtain (1) from $z_i^{(k)} - u_i \leq \omega$ because $z^{(k)}, u \in B$, the fact that $\nu_i^{(k)}$ and $x_i^{(k)} - y_i^{(k)}$ are positive, and $1 = \overline{\nabla_i f_r}(x^{(k)}) \leq \nabla_i f_r(x^{(k)})$, $0 < \nu_i^{(k)} \leq \nabla_i f_r(x^{(k)})$.

- If $\nu_i^{(k)} > 0$ and $z_i^{(k)} = -\omega$ then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \eta_k \nu_i^{(k)} (z_i^{(k-1)} - u_i) + \eta_k^2 L \overline{\nabla_i f_r}(x^{(k)}) (x_i^{(k)} - y_i^{(k)}) \\
 & \stackrel{\textcircled{1}}{\leq} \eta_k \nabla_i f_r(x^{(k)}) (z_i^{(k-1)} - z_i^{(k)}) + \eta_k^2 L \nabla_i f_r(x^{(k)}) (x_i^{(k)} - y_i^{(k)}) \\
 & \stackrel{\textcircled{2}}{\leq} \eta_k^2 L \nabla_i f_r(x^{(k)}) (x_i^{(k)} - y_i^{(k)}) + \eta_k^2 L \nabla_i f_r(x^{(k)}) (x_i^{(k)} - y_i^{(k)}) \\
 & \leq \frac{3}{2} \eta_k L \nabla_i f_r(x^{(k)}) (x_i^{(k)} - y_i^{(k)}).
 \end{aligned}$$

We have $\textcircled{1}$ because in this case, $u_i - z_i^{(k)}$, $x_i^{(k)} - y_i^{(k)}$, $\nu_i^{(k)}$, $\overline{\nabla_i f_r}(x^{(k)})$ are all ≥ 0 . We also used $0 < \nu_i^{(k)} < \nabla_i f_r(x^{(k)})$, $0 < \overline{\nabla_i f_r}(x^{(k)}) < \nabla_i f_r(x^{(k)})$. In $\textcircled{2}$, we used $z_i^{(k-1)} - z_i^{(k)} = \eta_k L (x_i^{(k)} - y_i^{(k)})$. \blacksquare

Appendix C. Missing proofs from Section 3

Lemma 15 (Multiplicative Weights Lemma - Additive and Mult. Guarantee) *Let $\ell^{(k)} \in [-\sigma, \tau]^{\tilde{m}}$ be an sequence of \tilde{m} -dimensional arbitrary loss vectors, for $k \in [K]$ and $\sigma, \tau \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$. Denote $W^+ = \max\{\sigma, \tau\}$, $W^- = \min\{\sigma, \tau\}$. For a target accuracy $\delta \in (0, 2W^-]$, learning rate $\eta = \frac{\delta}{4W^-} \leq \frac{1}{2}$, and initial weights $\Lambda^{(1)} = \mathbf{1}_{\tilde{m}} \in \Delta^{\tilde{m}}$, inducing an initial uniform distribution, run the following multiplicative weights update rule*

$$\Lambda^{(k+1)} \leftarrow \Lambda^{(k)} \odot (\mathbf{1}_{\tilde{m}} - \frac{\eta}{W^+} \ell^{(k)}),$$

for $k = 1, \dots, K \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{8\sigma\tau \log(\tilde{m})}{\delta^2}$, where \odot represents the coordinate-wise product. Then, for every $u \in \Delta^{\tilde{m}}$ we have

$$\frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \left\langle \ell^{(k)}, \frac{\Lambda^{(k)}}{\|\Lambda^{(k)}\|_1} \right\rangle \leq \delta + \frac{1 + \text{sign}(\sigma, \tau)\eta}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \langle \ell^{(k)}, u \rangle,$$

where $\text{sign}(\sigma, \tau)$ is 1 if $\tau \geq \sigma$ and -1 otherwise.

Proof We assume without loss of generality that for a fixed $i \in [\tilde{m}]$ we have $u = e_i$. It is enough to prove the result in this case since the general case can be obtained as a convex combination of the resulting inequalities.

We use the potential function $\Phi^{(k)} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \|\Lambda^{(k)}\|_1$. On the one hand we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Phi^{(K+1)} & \stackrel{\textcircled{1}}{=} \sum_{i=1}^{\tilde{m}} \Lambda_i^{(K)} \left(1 - \frac{\eta}{W^+} \ell_i^{(K)} \right) \stackrel{\textcircled{2}}{=} \Phi^{(K)} - \frac{\eta}{W^+} \Phi^{(K)} \sum_{i=1}^{\tilde{m}} \ell_i^{(K)} \frac{\Lambda_i^{(K)}}{\|\Lambda^{(K)}\|_1} \\
 & = \Phi^{(K)} \left(1 - \frac{\eta}{W^+} \left\langle \ell^{(K)}, \frac{\Lambda^{(K)}}{\|\Lambda^{(K)}\|_1} \right\rangle \right) \stackrel{\textcircled{3}}{\leq} \Phi^{(K)} \exp \left(-\frac{\eta}{W^+} \left\langle \ell^{(K)}, \frac{\Lambda^{(K)}}{\|\Lambda^{(K)}\|_1} \right\rangle \right) \\
 & \stackrel{\textcircled{4}}{\leq} \Phi^{(1)} \exp \left(-\frac{\eta}{W^+} \sum_{k=1}^K \left\langle \ell^{(k)}, \frac{\Lambda^{(k)}}{\|\Lambda^{(k)}\|_1} \right\rangle \right) = \tilde{m} \cdot \exp \left(-\frac{\eta}{W^+} \sum_{k=1}^K \left\langle \ell^{(k)}, \frac{\Lambda^{(k)}}{\|\Lambda^{(k)}\|_1} \right\rangle \right).
 \end{aligned} \tag{25}$$

Here ① is due to the MW update rule and ② uses $\Phi^{(K)} = \|\Lambda^{(K)}\|_1$. Now ③ uses $1 - x \leq e^{-x}$, for all $x \in \mathbb{R}$. We recursively applied all of the previous inequalities to obtain ④.

On the other hand, we can lower bound

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi^{(K+1)} &\stackrel{\textcircled{1}}{\geq} \Lambda_i^{(K+1)} \stackrel{\textcircled{2}}{=} \Lambda_i^{(1)} \prod_{k=1}^K \left(1 - \frac{\eta}{W^+} \ell_i^{(k)}\right) \\ &\stackrel{\textcircled{3}}{\geq} (1 - \eta)^{\frac{1}{W^+} \sum_{\{k: \ell_i^{(k)} \geq 0\}} \ell_i^{(k)}} \cdot (1 + \eta)^{\frac{1}{W^+} \sum_{\{k: \ell_i^{(k)} < 0\}} \ell_i^{(k)}}, \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

where ① holds by the definition of $\Phi^{(K+1)}$ as $\|\Lambda^{(K+1)}\|_1$. Here, ② uses the MW update rule and ③ is due to Bernoulli's inequality: $1 + rx \geq (1 + x)^r$, for $-1 \leq x$, $0 \leq r \leq 1$, with $(x, r) \in \{(-\eta, \ell_i^{(k)}/W^+), (\eta, -\ell_i^{(k)}/W^+)\}$.

Combining (25) and (26), taking logarithms, and multiplying by $\frac{W^+}{\eta}$ we obtain the following inequality ①, which we further bound:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{W^+ \log(\tilde{m})}{\eta} - \sum_{k=1}^K \left\langle \ell^{(k)}, \frac{\Lambda^{(k)}}{\|\Lambda^{(k)}\|_1} \right\rangle &\stackrel{\textcircled{1}}{\geq} \frac{1}{\eta} \log(1 - \eta) \left(\sum_{\{k: \ell_i^{(k)} \geq 0\}} \ell_i^{(k)} \right) - \frac{1}{\eta} \log(1 + \eta) \left(\sum_{\{k: \ell_i^{(k)} < 0\}} \ell_i^{(k)} \right) \\ &\stackrel{\textcircled{2}}{\geq} (-1 - \eta) \left(\sum_{\{k: \ell_i^{(k)} \geq 0\}} \ell_i^{(k)} \right) + (-1 + \eta) \left(\sum_{\{k: \ell_i^{(k)} < 0\}} \ell_i^{(k)} \right) \\ &\stackrel{\textcircled{3}}{\geq} -2\eta W^- K + (-1 - \text{sign}(\sigma, \tau)\eta) \sum_{k=1}^K \ell_i^{(k)}. \end{aligned}$$

In ②, we used $\log(1 - \eta) \geq -\eta - \eta^2$ and $\log(1 + \eta) \geq \eta - \eta^2$ for $\eta \leq 1/2$. For ③, we have two cases. If $\sigma > \tau$ we have $\text{sign}(\sigma, \tau) = -1$ and we use $-2\eta \ell_i^{(k)} \geq -2\eta\tau = -2\eta W^-$ and bound $-\sum_{k=1}^K \mathbb{1}_{\{k: \ell_i^{(k)} \geq 0\}} \geq -K$. Otherwise, we use $2\eta \ell_i^{(k)} \geq -2\eta\sigma = -2\eta W^-$ and bound $-\sum_{k=1}^K \mathbb{1}_{\{k: \ell_i^{(k)} < 0\}} \geq -K$. Reorganizing terms, dividing by K , and using $u = e_i$ we obtain

$$\frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \left\langle \ell^{(k)}, \frac{\Lambda^{(k)}}{\|\Lambda^{(k)}\|_1} \right\rangle \leq \frac{W^+ \log(\tilde{m})}{\eta K} + 2\eta W^- + \frac{1 + \text{sign}(\sigma, \tau)\eta}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \langle \ell^{(k)}, u \rangle,$$

and finally substituting the value of $\eta = \frac{\delta}{4W^-}$ and $K = \frac{8\sigma\tau \log(\tilde{m})}{\delta^2} = \frac{8W^+W^- \log(\tilde{m})}{\delta^2}$ in the statement we obtain the desired result:

$$\frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \left\langle \ell^{(k)}, \frac{\Lambda^{(k)}}{\|\Lambda^{(k)}\|_1} \right\rangle \leq \frac{\delta}{2} + \frac{\delta}{2} + \frac{1 + \text{sign}(\sigma, \tau)\eta}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \langle \ell^{(k)}, u \rangle.$$

■

Proof of Lemma 9. Since we assumed $\varepsilon < 4 \min\{\tau, \sigma\}$, the assumption on δ required by Lemma 15 is satisfied: $\delta = \varepsilon/2 < 2 \min\{\tau, \sigma\}$. The dimension of the statement was $\tilde{m} = m$, but we assume

nothing on \tilde{m} , so in the proof below it can be that $\tilde{m} = |I_t|$, i.e., the dimension we obtain when we filter some constraints in [Algorithm 2](#). We would need to substitute the instances of A by A_{I_t} . With the parameters of the statement, we obtain the following inequality for any $u \in \Delta^m$:

$$0 \stackrel{\textcircled{1}}{\leq} \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \langle \mathbb{1}_m - Ap^{(k)}, \frac{\Lambda^{(k)}}{\|\Lambda^{(k)}\|_1} \rangle \stackrel{\textcircled{2}}{\leq} \frac{\varepsilon}{2} + \frac{1 + \text{sign}(\sigma, \tau)\eta}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \langle \mathbb{1}_m - Ap^{(k)}, u \rangle, \quad (27)$$

where $\textcircled{1}$ is satisfied by the oracle assumption [\(12\)](#), after using the fact that $\langle \mathbb{1}_m, \Lambda^{(k)} / \|\Lambda^{(k)}\|_1 \rangle = 1$. Inequality $\textcircled{2}$ is the guarantee of the MW algorithm, cf. [Lemma 15](#). We finally obtain the guarantee we had to prove:

$$-\varepsilon \stackrel{\textcircled{1}}{\leq} -\frac{\varepsilon}{2(1 + \text{sign}(\sigma, \tau)\eta)} \stackrel{\textcircled{2}}{\leq} 1 - \langle A_i, \bar{p} \rangle, \quad \text{for all } i \in [m],$$

where $\bar{p} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K p^{(k)}$. Here $\textcircled{1}$ holds regardless of the value of $\text{sign}(\sigma, \tau)$, due to the choice of $\eta \leq 1/2$. Furthermore, $\textcircled{2}$ is obtained by setting $u = e_i$ for all $i \in [m]$ and simplifying [\(27\)](#). \blacksquare

C.1. Missing proofs from [Section 3.3](#)

The first lemma shows that the oracle returns a point in the lens $\mathcal{L}_{\omega\delta}(v)$ efficiently.

Lemma 16 *Let $v \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} c(s)/(1 + \delta) \in \mathcal{P}$. The feasibility oracle returns a point in the intersection $\mathcal{L}_{\omega\delta}(v) \cap \{x \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n : \langle q, x \rangle \leq 1\}$ in time $O(n \log(\frac{n}{(\omega-1)\delta} + \frac{n}{\omega-1}))$.*

Proof The output point o has to satisfy $\textcircled{1} : \langle c^{-1}(o), v \rangle \leq 1$ and $\textcircled{2} : \langle c^{-1}(v), o \rangle \leq 1 + \omega\delta$ to be in the lens and $\textcircled{3} : \langle q, o \rangle \leq 1$ to be in the halfspace defined by q .

We note that the definition of $c(\cdot)$ implies $c^{-1}(v) = (1 + \delta)s$. Condition $\textcircled{1}$ is always trivially satisfied because $c^{-1}(o) \in \mathcal{D}$ and $v \in \mathcal{P}$ by construction.

Now we have three cases. If $\langle s, c(q) \rangle \leq \frac{1+\omega\delta}{1+\delta}$ the oracle returns $o = c(q)$ and $\lambda^{(o)} = \lambda^{(q)}$. This satisfies the other two conditions. Indeed, $\textcircled{3}$ comes from $\langle q, c(q) \rangle = 1$ and $\textcircled{2}$ is satisfied because $\langle s, c(q) \rangle \leq \frac{1+\omega\delta}{1+\delta}$ implies $\langle c^{-1}(v), c(q) \rangle = \langle (1 + \delta)s, c(q) \rangle \leq 1 + \omega\delta$. If we have $\langle q, c(s) \rangle \leq 1$, then the oracle returns $o = c(s)$ and $\lambda^{(o)} = \lambda^{(s)}$. In this case $\textcircled{3}$ is satisfied by construction, and $\textcircled{2}$ is satisfied because $\langle c^{-1}(v), c(s) \rangle = \langle (1 + \delta)s, c(s) \rangle = 1 + \delta \leq 1 + \omega\delta$.

From now on we may focus on the third case, where $\langle s, c(q) \rangle > \frac{1+\omega\delta}{1+\delta}$ and $\langle q, c(s) \rangle > 1$. Let us define the functions $\pi_s, \pi_q : (0, 1) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ as:

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_s(\mu) &= \langle s, c((1 - \mu)s + \mu q) \rangle, \\ \pi_q(\mu) &= \langle q, c((1 - \mu)s + \mu q) \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

The key observation relating these two functions is $(1 - \mu)\pi_s(\mu) + \mu\pi_q(\mu) = 1$ for any $\mu \in (0, 1)$ because $\langle h, c(h) \rangle = 1$ for any constraint $h \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n$. So, if we find a $\mu^* \in (0, 1)$ with $\pi_s(\mu^*) \in (1, \frac{1+\omega\delta}{1+\delta})$ then $o = c((1 - \mu^*)s + \mu^*q)$ will satisfy both $\textcircled{2}$, because of $\pi_s(\mu^*) < (1 + \omega\delta)/(1 + \delta)$, and also $\textcircled{3}$, because if $\pi_s(\mu^*) > 1$ then $\pi_q(\mu^*) < 1$ by the observation. And we recover $\lambda^{(o)}$ as $(1 - \mu^*)\lambda^{(s)} + \mu^*\lambda^{(q)}$.

We intend to find such a μ^* with the bisection method. Despite π_s having a potential singularity near $\mu = 1$, we will show it is regular enough to guarantee fast convergence. By the assumptions, $\lim_{\mu \rightarrow 1} \pi_s(\mu) > \frac{1+\omega\delta}{1+\delta}$ and $\lim_{\mu \rightarrow 0} \pi_q(\mu) > 1$. Then, $\pi_q(\mu) > 1$ for any μ small enough, which means $\pi_s(\mu) < 1$ for any μ small enough by the observation. Finally, π_s is continuous, so we are able to find μ^* with $\pi_s(\mu^*) \in (1, \frac{1+\omega\delta}{1+\delta})$ via the bisection method. The only remaining question is computing its running time, for which we lower bound the length of an interval in $(0, 1)$ that satisfies the conditions.

For that we will bound $\pi'_s(\mu)$. Let us start with the definition of $\pi'_s(\mu)/\pi_s(\mu)$. Let $\pi_s(\mu)_i \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{s_i}{n((1-\mu)s_i + \mu q_i)}$ be the i -th summand in the inner product of $\pi_s(\mu)$. We have

$$\frac{\pi'_s(\mu)}{\pi_s(\mu)} = \frac{\sum_{i \in [n]} \frac{s_i n (s_i - q_i)}{n^2 ((1-\mu)s_i + \mu q_i)^2}}{\sum_{i \in [n]} \pi_s(\mu)_i} = \frac{\sum_{i \in [n]} \pi_s(\mu)_i \frac{(s_i - q_i)}{(1-\mu)s_i + \mu q_i}}{\sum_{i \in [n]} \pi_s(\mu)_i}.$$

We have $\pi_s(\mu)_i \geq 0$ so the expression above is a weighted arithmetic mean, and its value is at most that of the maximum of the summands:

$$\frac{\pi'_s(\mu)}{\pi_s(\mu)} \leq \max_{i \in [n]} \frac{s_i - q_i}{(1-\mu)s_i + \mu q_i} \stackrel{\textcircled{1}}{\leq} n \max_{i \in [n]} \pi_s(\mu)_i \leq n \sum_{i \in [n]} \pi_s(\mu)_i \leq n \pi_s(\mu).$$

We dropped $-q_i/((1-\mu)s_i + \mu q_i)$ in $\textcircled{1}$ above. Hence, we have $\pi'_s(\mu) \leq n \pi_s^2(\mu)$. This means the preimage of $J \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (1, \frac{1+\omega\delta}{1+\delta})$ is an interval of length at least

$$\frac{\frac{1+\omega\delta}{1+\delta} - 1}{\max_{\mu: \pi_s(\mu) \in J} \pi'_s(\mu)} \geq \frac{\frac{1+\omega\delta}{1+\delta} - 1}{\max_{\mu: \pi_s(\mu) \in J} n \pi_s^2(\mu)} = \frac{\frac{1+\omega\delta}{1+\delta} - 1}{n \left(\frac{1+\omega\delta}{1+\delta} \right)^2}.$$

We are interested in upper bounding the inverse of the length:

$$\frac{n \left(\frac{1+\omega\delta}{1+\delta} \right)^2}{\frac{1+\omega\delta}{1+\delta} - 1} = \frac{n(1+\omega\delta)^2}{(\omega-1)\delta(1+\delta)} = n \left(\frac{1}{(\omega-1)\delta} + \frac{2\omega-1}{\omega-1} + \frac{\delta(\omega-1)}{1+\delta} \right) \leq \frac{n}{(\omega-1)\delta} + \frac{4n}{\omega-1}.$$

Since the bisection method starts with an interval of length 1 and progressively halves it every iteration, it takes at most $\log_2 \left(\frac{n}{(\omega-1)\delta} + \frac{4n}{\omega-1} \right)$ iterations to find a point with $\pi_s(\mu^*) \in (1, \frac{1+\omega\delta}{1+\delta})$, and each step takes $O(n)$ in processing time. Thus, the oracle returns a point in time $O(n \log \left(\frac{n}{(\omega-1)\delta} + \frac{4n}{\omega-1} \right))$. \blacksquare

The following lemma bounds the lens by a box defined in terms of $\omega\delta$.

Lemma 17 *If $x \in \mathcal{L}_{\omega\delta}(v)$, with $v \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n$, $\omega\delta > 0$, then,*

$$\begin{aligned} x_i &\geq L_i \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \max(0, 1 - \sqrt{\omega\delta n})v_i, \\ x_i &\leq U_i \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (1 + \sqrt{\omega\delta n} + \omega\delta n)v_i. \end{aligned}$$

We call the region $\prod_i [L_i, U_i]$ the bounding box of the lens.

Proof of Lemma 17. Recall that the lens is defined as the set of points $x \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n$ satisfying both $\langle c^{-1}(v), x \rangle \leq 1 + \omega\delta$ and $\langle c^{-1}(x), v \rangle \leq 1$. Let us rewrite these conditions as sums:

$$\begin{cases} \langle c^{-1}(v), x \rangle = \sum_{i \in [n]} \frac{x_i}{nv_i} \leq 1 + \omega\delta, \\ \langle c^{-1}(x), v \rangle = \sum_{i \in [n]} \frac{v_i}{nx_i} \leq 1. \end{cases}$$

These two constraints are invariant up to multiplications of x_i and v_i by the same constant. Let $z_i = x_i/v_i$, and multiply both by n to get:

$$\begin{cases} \sum_{i \in [n]} z_i \leq (1 + \omega\delta)n, \\ \sum_{i \in [n]} z_i^{-1} \leq n. \end{cases}$$

It is our purpose to find the maximum and minimum of z_i in this region. Because the system is symmetric under reordering of the z_i , we may focus on bounding z_1 . Since the region is convex and symmetric under reordering of the variables, and because the function $z \mapsto z_1$ is symmetric under reordering of the last $(n-1)$ variables, we may also assume that the maximum and minimum of this function are attained in points with $z_2 = \dots = z_n$.

This brings us to:

$$\begin{cases} z_1 + (n-1)z_2 \leq (1 + \omega\delta)n, \\ z_1^{-1} + (n-1)z_2^{-1} \leq n. \end{cases}$$

The two constraints independently will never have normals vectors proportional to e_1 . Furthermore the feasible region of the second constraint in $\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n$ is contained in the interior of $\mathbb{R}_{> 0}^n$. This means that the solutions maximizing and minimizing z_1 must satisfy both constraints with equality.

Solving the system of equations gives two roots. The two solutions for z_1 are:

$$\begin{aligned} z_1^+ &= \frac{1}{2}(\omega\delta n + 2 + \sqrt{\omega^2\delta^2 n^2 + 4\omega\delta n - 4\omega\delta}), \\ z_1^- &= \frac{1}{2}(\omega\delta n + 2 - \sqrt{\omega^2\delta^2 n^2 + 4\omega\delta n - 4\omega\delta}). \end{aligned}$$

Let us bound the smaller one first. We give two such lower bounds. The trivial one is that $z_1^- > 0$. This comes from the fact that the second constraint already guarantees $z_i > 0$.

The second lower bound comes from $\sqrt{a+b} \leq \sqrt{a} + \sqrt{b}$ for $a, b > 0$, a consequence of the triangle inequality:

$$\begin{aligned} z_1^- &= \frac{1}{2}(\omega\delta n + 2 - \sqrt{\omega^2\delta^2 n^2 + 4\omega\delta n - 4\omega\delta}) \geq \frac{1}{2}(\omega\delta n + 2 - \sqrt{\omega^2\delta^2 n^2 + 4\omega\delta n}) \geq \\ &\geq \frac{1}{2}(\omega\delta n + 2 - \omega\delta n - 2\sqrt{\omega\delta n}) \geq 1 - \sqrt{\omega\delta n}. \end{aligned}$$

Now let us study the larger root. As with the other root, we remove the $-4\omega\delta$ term in the square root, then apply the triangle inequality:

$$\begin{aligned} z_1^+ &= \frac{1}{2}(\omega\delta n + 2 + \sqrt{\omega^2\delta^2 n^2 + 4\omega\delta n - 4\omega\delta}) \leq \frac{1}{2}(\omega\delta n + 2 + \sqrt{\omega^2\delta^2 n^2 + 4\omega\delta n}) \leq \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2}(\omega\delta n + 2 + \omega\delta n + 2\sqrt{\omega\delta n}) \geq 1 + \omega\delta n + \sqrt{\omega\delta n}. \end{aligned}$$

Undoing the change of variables $z_i = x_i/v_i$ we obtain the desired bounds. ■

Observe that indeed the optimum p^{λ^*} satisfies the two conditions in the definition of $\mathcal{L}_{\omega\delta}(v)$: The first condition $\langle c^{-1}(p^{\lambda^*}), v \rangle \leq 1$ comes from $p^{\lambda^*} \in c(\mathcal{D})$, so $c^{-1}(p^{\lambda^*}) \in \mathcal{D}$ covers \mathcal{P} , i.e., $\langle c^{-1}(p^{\lambda^*}), x \rangle \leq 1$ for all $x \in \mathcal{P}$. In particular it covers v . The second condition $\langle c^{-1}(v), p^{\lambda^*} \rangle \leq 1 + \omega\delta$ is equivalent to $\langle \frac{1+\delta}{1+\omega\delta}v, p^{\lambda^*} \rangle \leq 1$. Since $\omega > 1$, this is satisfied as $p^{\lambda^*} \in \mathcal{P}$ and $v \in \mathcal{D}$ and therefore $\frac{1+\delta}{1+\omega\delta}v \in \mathcal{D}^+$. The last two lemmas provide the intuition of why the oracle returns points that are not too far from p^{λ^*} : for a fixed $\omega > 1$ the bounding boxes of the respective lenses get smaller as $\delta \rightarrow 0$.

Now we can finally prove the exact guarantees of the oracle. Let $q = A^T \lambda^{(q)}$ with $\lambda^{(q)} \in \Delta^m$ be the query. Furthermore, let $s = A^T \lambda^{(s)}$ with $\lambda^{(s)} \in \Delta^m$ be our current good solution, so that the point $c(s) = c(A^T \lambda^{(s)})$ satisfies $\hat{g}(c(s)) \leq 1 + \delta$. The following proposition proves the guarantees on the oracle.

Proposition 18 *Let $U \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} c(s)(1 + 2\delta n + \sqrt{2\delta n})/(1 + \delta)$ be the upper-most vertex of the bounding box of the lens $\mathcal{L}_{\omega\delta}(v)$, as defined in Lemma 17. Let I be the set of non-redundant constraints, defined as $I \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{i \in [m] : \langle A_i, U \rangle \geq 1\}$. Furthermore, let the following be the width parameters of the oracle \mathfrak{D} implemented in Algorithm 3:*

$$\sigma \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \min(\sqrt{\omega\delta n} + \omega\delta n, \frac{1 + \omega\delta}{1 + \delta} \max_{i \in [n]} \frac{1}{s_i} - 1) \quad \text{and} \quad \tau \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \min(3\sqrt{\omega\delta n}, 1). \quad (28)$$

Then, the oracle \mathfrak{D} in Algorithm 3 returns a pair $\lambda^{(o)} \in \Delta^m$, $o \in c(\mathcal{D})$ such that

1. o satisfies q , i.e., $\langle q, o \rangle \leq 1$.
2. If $i \in I$, it yields $\langle A_i, o \rangle \in [1 - \tau, 1 + \sigma]$. That is, it is compatible with the width parameters σ, τ as above, with the loss $1 - \langle A_i, o \rangle$ in $[-\sigma, \tau]$.
3. o satisfies all redundant constraints, i.e., $\langle A_i, o \rangle \leq 1$, if $i \in [m] \setminus I$.

Besides, $o = c(A^T \lambda^{(o)})$, and Algorithm 3 runs in time $O(n \log(\frac{n}{(\omega-1)\delta} + \frac{n}{\omega-1}))$.

Proof The first claim is proven in Lemma 16.

Let us consider I now. It is clear that the constraints in I are exactly those that do not cover the bounding box of Lemma 17 around the lens $\mathcal{L}_{\omega\delta}(v)$, with $v \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} c(s)/(1 + \delta)$. This is because a positive constraint covers a box if and only if it covers the upper-most vertex U . Since the oracle returns a point in the lens, and hence in the box, any constraint not in I is automatically satisfied by any point returned by the oracle. This is the third claim.

Note that the geometric meaning of the second claim is that o is close to be lying on the hyperplanes $\langle A_i, x \rangle = 1$. If $i \in I$, then $\langle A_i, U \rangle \geq 1$ by the definition of I . Define L as the lower-most vertex of the bounding box of $\mathcal{L}_{\omega\delta}(v)$. Now,

$$\langle A_i, o \rangle \geq \min_{x \in \mathcal{L}_{\omega\delta}(v)} \langle A_i, x \rangle \geq \min\{\langle A_i, x \rangle : x \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n, x_i \in [L_i, U_i]\}.$$

And the second minimum will be attained in the lower-most vertex as $A_{ij} \geq 0$ for all $j \in [n]$. Therefore:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle A_i, o \rangle &\geq \min_{x \in \mathcal{L}(v, \omega\delta)} \langle A_i, x \rangle \geq \langle A_i, L \rangle = \langle A_i, U \rangle \frac{\max(0, 1 - \sqrt{\omega\delta n})}{1 + \sqrt{\omega\delta n} + \omega\delta n} \\ &\geq \frac{\max(0, 1 - \sqrt{\omega\delta n})}{1 + \sqrt{\omega\delta n} + \omega\delta n} = 1 - \min\left(1, \frac{2\sqrt{\omega\delta n} + \omega\delta n}{1 + \sqrt{\omega\delta n} + \omega\delta n}\right). \end{aligned}$$

The second argument of the min is only less than 1 whenever $\omega\delta n < 1$, so we may assume the latter in order to obtain the following bound

$$\langle A_i, o \rangle \geq \min_{x \in \mathcal{L}(v, \omega\delta)} \langle A_i, x \rangle \geq 1 - \min \left(1, \frac{2\sqrt{\omega\delta n} + \omega\delta n}{1 + \sqrt{\omega\delta n} + \omega\delta n} \right) \geq 1 - \min(1, 3\sqrt{\omega\delta n}) = 1 - \tau.$$

Finally, we focus on the bound with σ . As before, the maximum of $\langle A_i, x \rangle$ will be attained at a vertex of the box, only this time it is U . Now, as $v \in \mathcal{P}$, we have $\langle A_i, v \rangle \leq 1$. We use these two facts to conclude:

$$\langle A_i, o \rangle \leq \max_{x \in \mathcal{L}(v, \omega\delta)} \langle A_i, x \rangle \leq \langle A_i, U \rangle = \langle A_i, v \rangle (1 + \sqrt{\omega\delta n} + \omega\delta n) \leq 1 + \sqrt{\omega\delta n} + \omega\delta n.$$

The second upper bound on $\langle A_i, o \rangle$ does not come from the bounding box. We only look at the linear component of the lens, and since A_i is positive, it must attain a maximum in one of the vertices of the simplex in the intersection of the hyperplane with the positive orthant. We also use that $A_{ij} \leq 1$:

$$\langle A_i, o \rangle \leq \max_{x \in \mathcal{L}_{\omega\delta}(v)} \langle A_i, x \rangle \leq \max_{\substack{x \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n \\ \langle s, x \rangle \leq (1+\omega\delta)/(1+\delta)}} \langle A_i, x \rangle = \max_{j \in [n]} A_{ij} \frac{1 + \omega\delta}{1 + \delta} \frac{1}{s_j} \leq \frac{1 + \omega\delta}{1 + \delta} \max_{j \in [n]} \frac{1}{s_j}.$$

Thus, $\langle A_i, o \rangle \leq 1 + \min(\sqrt{\omega\delta n} + \omega\delta n, \frac{1+\omega\delta}{1+\delta} \max_{j \in [n]} \frac{1}{s_j} - 1) = 1 + \sigma$.

The running time and the fact $o = c(A^T \lambda^{(o)})$ follow from [Lemma 16](#). ■

Appendix D. Analysis of the Yamnitsky Levin algorithm

The analysis of [\(YL82\)](#) shows a bound on the volume ratio between two consecutive bounding simplices. Affine automorphisms preserve volume ratios, so we can assume without loss of generality that $\Delta^{(k)} \subset \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n$, $v^{(k)} = \mathbb{0}_n$ and that the i -th facet incident to $v^{(k)}$ is normal to e_i . In that case, the set of constraints \mathcal{H}_v consists of non-negative hyperplanes. The volume of the simplex bounded by a hyperplane $h \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n$ and the first orthant is given by $\frac{1}{n!} \prod_{i \in [n]} h_i^{-1}$. Thus, the volume minimization problem occurring in a stage of the YL algorithm, when we fix a vertex $v^{(k)}$ is equivalent to problem [\(IFP-Dual\)](#), as the latter corresponds to the logarithm of this volume, up to an additive constant, when $h = A^T \lambda$. We assume without loss of generality that the collection of constraints \mathcal{H}_v forms a matrix A satisfying [\(1\)](#).

We present, in [Algorithm 4](#), a direct translation of the YL simplices algorithm [\(YL82\)](#) running for a stage and restricted to the positive orthant. This algorithm represents exactly what the YL algorithm would do should we run it on the polyhedron $\mathcal{P} = \{x \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n : Ax \leq \mathbf{1}_m\}$ with initial simplex being the intersection of the positive orthant and the initial hyperplane $s \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j \in [n]} A_{\ell_j}$, where $\ell_j \in \arg \max_{i \in [m]} A_{ij}$. Let $\lambda^{(s)} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j \in [n]} e_{\ell_j} \in \Delta^m$, where e_i is the i -th element of the canonical base, and note $s = h^{\lambda^{(s)}} = A^T \lambda^{(s)}$. This is a natural initial simplex and is in general a better choice than the one in the classical YL algorithm. Further, in contrast, it does not depend on the bit complexity of the polyhedron. The choice of s guarantees that the volume of the initial

simplex is at most $\frac{n^n}{n!}$, as for all $j \in [n]$, we have $s_j \geq A_{\ell_j, j}/n = 1/n$, where the last equality holds by (1).

For completeness, we provide below a proof on the running time of [Algorithm 4](#), which is an adaption of the one of [\(YL82\)](#) to this context. Recall that a stage ends when the constraints cover the centroid of the bounding simplex $\Delta^{(k)}$, or equivalently when $\hat{g}(p^{\lambda^{(k)}}) \leq 1 + 1/n$. [Algorithm 4](#) takes $\tilde{O}(Nn^3)$ operations to run while our [Algorithm 2](#) takes $\tilde{O}(Nn^2)$, cf. [Theorem 10](#) with $\varepsilon = 1$. Our algorithm shows how one can improve by exploiting the fact that the corner is fixed during a stage while the analysis of the YL algorithm does not require to be run in stages of this kind. Both algorithms use similar initial information. [Algorithm 4](#) is actually better informed, as the initial hyperplane s is coordinate-wise tighter than the one we use in [Algorithm 2](#). However this does not affect our bounds as in the worst case they are the same constraint.

Algorithm 4 Optimization of the dual of 1-fair packing with the Yamnitsky-Levin algorithm

Input: A matrix $A \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^{m \times n}$ with $A_{ij} \in [0, 1]$ for all $i \in [m], j \in [n]$.

```

1:  $k \leftarrow 1$ 
2:  $\lambda^{(k)} \leftarrow \lambda^{(s)} \in \Delta^m$ 
3: while  $\max_{j \in [m]} \langle A_j, p^{\lambda^{(k)}} \rangle > 1 + \frac{1}{n}$  do
4:    $j^{(k)} \leftarrow \arg \max_{j \in [m]} \langle A_j, p^{\lambda^{(k)}} \rangle$ 
5:    $\lambda^{(k+1)} \leftarrow (1 - \frac{1}{n^2})\lambda^{(k)} + \frac{1}{n^2}e_{j^{(k)}}$ 
6:    $k \leftarrow k + 1$ 
7: end while
8: return  $\lambda^{(k)}, h^{\lambda^{(k)}}$ 
    
```

Lemma 19 *Let \mathcal{P} be the polyhedron defined by $\mathcal{P} = \{x \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n : Ax \leq \mathbf{1}_m\}$ where $A \in \mathcal{M}_{m \times n}(\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0})$ satisfies (1). Assume we run [Algorithm 4](#) with the initial simplex defined above. Then [Algorithm 4](#) finds a feasible constraint $h \in \mathcal{D}$ with $\hat{g}(h) \leq 1 + 1/n$ in $\tilde{O}(n^3)$ iterations.*

Proof If [Algorithm 4](#) stops after K iterations, it must return a feasible constraint with $\hat{g}(h^{\lambda^{(K)}}) \leq 1 + 1/n$ because of the condition on the loop. Now let us prove its bound on the running time.

The volume of the initial simplex is at most $n^n/n!$, as we explained in its definition. The volume of \mathcal{P} is at least $1/n!$ since the elements of the canonical base e_i are in \mathcal{P} , for all $i \in [n]$. We will show now that after each iteration of the loop, the volume is reduced by a factor of $\exp(-1/(2(n+1)^2))$.

Let $s^{(k)} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} A^T \lambda^{(k)}$ be the hyperplane corresponding to $\lambda^{(k)}$ in [Algorithm 4](#), and let $h^{(k)}$ be the hyperplane $A_{j^{(k)}}$ chosen at iteration k . If the loop has not stopped yet, then $\langle h^{(k)}, c(s^{(k)}) \rangle > 1 + 1/n$ by the loop condition. The volume of the simplex $\Delta^{(k+1)}$ associated with $s^{(k+1)}$ is:

$$\text{vol}(\Delta^{(k+1)}) = \frac{1}{n!} \prod_{i \in [n]} \left(\left(1 - \frac{1}{n^2} \right) s_i^{(k)} + \frac{1}{n^2} h_i^{(k)} \right)^{-1}. \quad (29)$$

This expression, seen as a function of $h^{(k)}$, is strictly decreasing in each coordinate. Since $\langle h^{(k)}, c(s^{(k)}) \rangle > 1 + 1/n$, the volume is only made larger if we assumed $\langle h^{(k)}, c(s^{(k)}) \rangle = 1 + 1/n$ instead, by reducing each coordinate appropriately.

Furthermore since the right hand side is log-convex in the variables $h^{(k)}$, and the set $\{h \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^n : \langle h^{(k)}, c(s^{(k)}) \rangle = 1 + 1/n\}$ is a polytope, then Equation (29) must attain a maximum in one of the vertices. These vertices are the points $(n+1)s_i^{(k)}e_i$ for $i \in [n]$. We replace $h^{(k)}$ by any of them (the choice does not matter as we will soon see), and divide everything by $\text{vol}(\Delta^{(k)})$ to get:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\text{vol}(\Delta^{(k+1)})}{\text{vol}(\Delta^{(k)})} &\stackrel{\textcircled{1}}{\leq} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n^2}\right)^{-(n-1)} \left(\left(1 - \frac{1}{n^2}\right) + \frac{1}{n^2}(n+1)\right)^{-1} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{n^2}\right)^{-(n-1)} \left(1 + \frac{1}{n}\right)^{-1} \\ &= \left(1 + \frac{1}{n^2-1}\right)^{n-1} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n+1}\right) \stackrel{\textcircled{2}}{\leq} \exp\left(\frac{n-1}{n^2-1}\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{n+1}\right) \\ &\stackrel{\textcircled{3}}{\leq} \exp\left(\frac{n-1}{n^2-1} - \frac{1}{n+1} - \frac{1}{2(n+1)^2}\right) = \exp\left(\frac{-1}{2(n+1)^2}\right). \end{aligned}$$

In $\textcircled{1}$ we substituted $h^{(k)}$ by $(n+1)s_i^{(k)}e_i$. The choice of the index $i \in [n]$ is irrelevant, as all choices lead to the same bound. We also used the volume formula (29). In particular $\text{vol}(\Delta^{(k)}) = \frac{1}{n!} \prod_{i \in [n]} 1/s_i^{(k)}$. In $\textcircled{2}$ we apply $1+x \leq e^x$ to the first multiplicand for $x = \frac{1}{n^2-1}$. In $\textcircled{3}$ we used $\ln(1+x) \leq -\sum_{k=1}^2 (-x)^k/k$ for $x = -1/(n+1)$. This inequality holds for $x \in (-1, 0)$ by the Taylor series expansion of the logarithm at $x = 1$.

Finally, since the initial volume is at most $n^n/n!$ and the final volume is at least $1/n!$, this algorithm takes at most $\frac{n \log(n)}{1/2(n+1)^2} \in \tilde{O}(n^3)$ iterations to finalize. Note an iteration takes $O(N)$ operations. \blacksquare